

Master's thesis

February 2001

C^* -algebras associated to general shift spaces

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Preface

In 1980 Cuntz and Krieger introduced a class of C^* -algebra, known as the Cuntz-Krieger algebras, which has had an enormous influence on operator algebra and symbolic dynamics. It is naturally to see the Cuntz-Krieger algebras as C^* -algebras associated with topological Markov chains.

Since a topological Markov chain is an example of a shift space, it seems naturally to try to associate C^* -algebras with general shift spaces in a way that generalizes the Cuntz-Krieger algebras.

Kengo Matsumoto did that in 1997 and has in a series of papers described many of these C^* -algebras property. Unfortunately there is a fundamental mistake in one of Matsumoto's paper, so the C^* -algebra Matsumoto defined did not have all of the described properties. In this thesis I will to a general shift space associate a C^* -algebra with the properties Matsumoto thought the C^* -algebra he defined had. I will do that by associating to every shift space a Hilbert bimodule and then to that associate the C^* -algebra Pimsner has associated to a Hilbert bimodule.

The shift spaces Matsumoto worked with are two-sided, but it seems more naturally to me to work with one-sided shift spaces.

In Chapter 1 we begin with a short introduction to one-sided shift spaces. In Chapter 2 we sum up the definition and some of the fundamental properties of the C^* -algebra Pimsner has associated with a Hilbert bimodule, and we construct the Hilbert bimodule and then the C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ associated with a one-sided shift space. In Chapter 3 we look at some of the properties of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$. For example that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is a generalization of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras. Chapter 4 deals with conjugacy invariants. We will show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is an invariant and we will compute the K - and the KK^{nuc} -theory of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$. In Chapter 5 we will show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is isomorphic to a Cuntz-Krieger algebra when Λ is a sofic shift.

Each chapter is followed by some short notes which explain where the material covered in the chapter originate from.

Chapter 1

One-sided shift spaces

I will start by defining one-sided shift spaces and describe some of their properties. The definition and properties of one-sided shift spaces are very similar to the definition and properties of two-sided shift spaces as described in [10]. Shift spaces are also called subshifts, but we will stick to the term shift space.

Let $\mathfrak{A}$ be a finite set endowed with the discrete topology. We will call this set the alphabet. Let $\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ be the infinite product spaces $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathfrak{A}$ endowed with the product topology. The transformation σ on $\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ given by $(\sigma(x))_i = x_{i+1}$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$ is called the shift. Let Λ be a shift invariant closed subset of $\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ (by shift invariant we mean that $\sigma(\Lambda) \subseteq \Lambda$, not necessarily $\sigma(\Lambda) = \Lambda$, cf. Section 3.4). The topological dynamical system $(\Lambda, \sigma|_{\Lambda})$ is called a one-sided shift space. We will denote $\sigma|_{\Lambda}$ by σ_{Λ} or σ for simplicity, and on occasion the alphabet $\mathfrak{A}$ by $\mathfrak{A}_{\Lambda}$.

Clearly, for every alphabet $\mathfrak{A}$, $\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ is a one-sided shift space. We call $\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ for the full (one-sided) $\mathfrak{A}$ -shift.

A finite sequence $\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_k)$ of elements $\mu_j \in \mathfrak{A}$ is called a finite word. The length of μ is k and is denoted by $|\mu|$. We let for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda)$ be the set of all words with length k appearing in some $x \in \Lambda$. We set $\mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda) = \bigcup_{k=0}^l \mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda)$ and $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \bigcup_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda)$, where $\mathcal{B}_0(\Lambda)$ denotes the empty word $\emptyset$. $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ is called the language of Λ . Note that $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}_{\Lambda}^{\mathbb{N}})$ for every one-sided shift space.

For a one-sided shift space Λ and a word $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ we denote by $C_{\Lambda}(\mu)$ the cylinder set

$$C_{\Lambda}(\mu) = \{x \in \Lambda \mid (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{|\mu|}) = \mu\}.$$

It is easy to see that

$$\{C_{\Lambda}(\mu) \mid \mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)\}$$

is a basis for the topology of Λ , and that $C_{\Lambda}(\mu)$ is closed and hence compact for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. We will allow us self to write $C(\mu)$ instead of $C_{\Lambda}(\mu)$ when it is clear which shift space we are working with.

Definition 1.0.1. Let Λ and Γ be one-sided shift spaces. A map $\phi : \Lambda \rightarrow \Gamma$ is called a sliding block code if it is continuous and $\phi \circ \sigma_\Lambda = \sigma_\Gamma \circ \phi$.

The morphisms in the category of one-sided shift spaces are the sliding block codes. The isomorphisms are called conjugacies and are of course defined in the following way:

Definition 1.0.2. Let Λ and Γ be two one-sided shift spaces. If there exists a homeomorphism $\psi : \Lambda \rightarrow \Gamma$ such that $\psi \circ \sigma_\Lambda = \sigma_\Gamma \circ \psi$ then we say that ψ is a conjugacy between Λ and Γ , that Λ and Γ are conjugate and we write $\Lambda \cong \Gamma$.

Proposition 1.0.3. The image of a sliding block code is a one-sided shift space.

Proof. Let Λ and Γ be one-sided shift spaces and $\phi : \Lambda \rightarrow \Gamma$ a sliding block code. We have to show that $\phi(\Lambda)$ is closed and shift invariant. Since ϕ is continuous and Λ is compact, $\phi(\Lambda)$ is compact and hence closed. Since $\phi \circ \sigma_\Lambda = \sigma_\Gamma \circ \phi$ and Λ is shift invariant, $\phi(\Lambda)$ is shift invariant. $\square$

The following will provide us with a lot of examples of one-sided shift spaces. Let $\mathfrak{A}$ be an alphabet and let $\mathcal{F}$ be a subset of $\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$. Let

$$X_{\mathcal{F}} = \{x \in \mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \mid \forall \mu \in \mathcal{F} : \mu \text{ does not appear in } x\}.$$

Proposition 1.0.4. Let $\mathfrak{A}$ be an alphabet. A subset Λ of $\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N}$ is a one-sided shift space if and only if there exists a subset $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$ such that $\Lambda = X_{\mathcal{F}}$.

Proof. First assume that $\Lambda = X_{\mathcal{F}}$ for some $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$. Then Λ is clearly shift invariant. We show that Λ is closed by showing that $\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \setminus \Lambda$ is open. So let $x \in \mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \setminus \Lambda$. Then there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$ such that $(x_m, x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{m+i}) \in \mathcal{F}$, and then

$$x \in C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{m+i})) \subseteq \mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \setminus \Lambda.$$

Hence $\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \setminus \Lambda$ is open.

Next assume that Λ is a one-sided shift space. Let

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N}) \mid \forall x \in \Lambda : \mu \text{ does not appear in } x\}.$$

We want to show that $\Lambda = X_{\mathcal{F}}$. Assume that $x \in \mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N} \setminus X_{\mathcal{F}}$. Then there exists a $\mu \in \mathcal{F}$ such that μ appear in x . So $x \notin \Lambda$. Hence $\Lambda \subseteq X_{\mathcal{F}}$.

Assume then that $x \in X_{\mathcal{F}}$. Then $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) \notin \mathcal{F}$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$. So $C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)) \neq \emptyset$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Since

$$C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{m+1})) \subseteq C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m))$$

and $C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m))$ is closed and hence compact for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\bigcap_{m \in \mathbb{N}} C_\Lambda((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)) \neq \emptyset.$$

That means that $x \in \Lambda$. So $X_{\mathcal{F}} \subseteq \Lambda$. $\square$

Example 1.0.5. Let A be a $n \times n$ -matrix with entries in $\{0, 1\}$. Let

$$\Lambda_A = \{(x_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}^{\mathbb{N}} \mid A(x_i, x_{i+1}) = 1\}.$$

Then $\Lambda_A = X_{\mathcal{F}}$, where

$$\mathcal{F} = \{(i, j) \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}^2 \mid A(i, j) = 0\},$$

and thus it follows from Proposition 1.0.4 that Λ_A is a one-sided shift space.

The one-sided shift spaces Λ_A defined in Example 1.0.5 are called topological Markov chains. We will return to them in Section 3.2.

We will now characterize the language of a one-sided shift space.

Proposition 1.0.6.

- a) Let Λ be a one-sided shift space, and let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. Then every subword of μ belongs to $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$, and there exists a nonempty word $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ such that $\mu\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$.
- b) Let $\mathfrak{A}$ be an alphabet, and let $\mathcal{L}$ be a subset of $\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ such that for every $\mu \in \mathcal{L}$, we have that every subword of μ belongs to $\mathcal{L}$, and there exists a nonempty word $\nu \in \mathcal{L}$ such that $\mu\nu \in \mathcal{L}$. Then $X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$ is the unique one-sided shift space with language $\mathcal{L}$.

Proof. a) Let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. Then μ appears in some $x \in \Lambda$. But then every subword of μ also appears in x and thus is in $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. Furthermore, clearly there is a nonempty word ν such that $\mu\nu$ appears in x and thus is in $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$.

b) Clearly $\mathcal{B}(X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}) \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. Let $\mu \in \mathcal{L}$. Then by repeatedly expanding μ , we get a $x \in \mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ such that $\mu = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{|\mu|})$ and every word that appears in x is in $\mathcal{L}$. Hence $x \in X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$, and $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}})$. Thus $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{B}(X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}})$.

Let $\Lambda = X_{\mathcal{F}}$ be a one-sided shift space such that $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \mathcal{L}$. If $x \in \Lambda$ then no word appearing in x is in $\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}$. So $x \in X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$. Hence $\Lambda \subseteq X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$. If $x \in X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$ then every word that appears in x belongs to $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \mathcal{B}(X_{\mathcal{F}})$ and thus cannot belong to $\mathcal{F}$. Hence $x \in X_{\mathcal{F}} = \Lambda$. Thus $\Lambda = X_{\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{L}}$. $\square$

Definition 1.0.7. A graph G consists of a finite set $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}(G)$ of vertices together with a finite set $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}(G)$ of edges. Each edge $e \in \mathcal{E}$ initiates at a vertex and terminates at a vertex. These vertices are called the initial state and the terminal state of e and are denoted by $i(e) \in \mathcal{V}$ and $t(e) \in \mathcal{V}$.

Definition 1.0.8. Let G be a graph. The edge shift Λ_G is the set

$$\Lambda_G = \{(x_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{E}(G)^{\mathbb{Z}} \mid t(x_i) = i(x_{i+1}) \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N}\}.$$

Proposition 1.0.9. *Let G be a graph. Then the edge shift Λ_G is a one-sided shift space.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{F}$ be the set $\{(e, f) \in \mathcal{E}(G)^2 \mid t(e) \neq i(f)\}$. Then $\Lambda_G = \Lambda_{\mathcal{F}}$. So Λ_G is a one-sided shift space by Proposition 1.0.4. $\square$

It is easy to see that every edge shift is a topological Markov chain. Not every topological Markov chain is an edge shift (cf. Example 2.3.1 in [10]), but one can show that every topological Markov chain is conjugate to an edge shift (cf. Proposition 2.3.9 in [10]).

Definition 1.0.10. *A labeled graph $\mathcal{G}$ is a pair $(G, \mathcal{L})$ of a graph G and a function $\mathcal{L} : \mathcal{E}(G) \rightarrow \mathfrak{A}$ from the edge set of G to an alphabet $\mathfrak{A}$.*

If $\mathcal{G} = (G, \mathcal{L})$ is a labeled graph, $\mathcal{L}$ can be extended to be a function defined on $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_G)$ and Λ_G simply by setting

$$\mathcal{L}((\mu_1, \dots, \mu_k)) = (\mathcal{L}(\mu_1), \dots, \mathcal{L}(\mu_k))$$

for $(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_k) \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_G)$ and

$$\mathcal{L}(x) = (y_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}},$$

where $y_i = \mathcal{L}(x_i)$, for $x = (x_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \in \Lambda_G$.

Definition 1.0.11. *Let $\mathcal{G} = (G, \mathcal{L})$ be a labeled graph. The set*

$$\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}} = \{\mathcal{L}(x) \mid x \in \Lambda_G\}$$

is called a sofic shift.

Theorem 1.0.12. *A sofic shift is a one-sided shift space.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{G} = (G, \mathcal{L})$ be a labeled graph, and let $\mathfrak{A}$ be the alphabet that $\mathcal{L}$ maps into. We want to show that $\mathcal{L}$ is a sliding block code. It is clear that $\mathcal{L} \circ \sigma_{\Lambda_G} = \sigma_{\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}} \circ \mathcal{L}$. Since for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1}(C_{\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}}(\mu)) = \bigcup_{\mathcal{L}(\nu)=\mu} C_{\Lambda_G}(\nu),$$

we have that $\mathcal{L} : \Lambda_G \rightarrow \mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}$ is continuous and hence a sliding block code. Thus $\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathcal{L}(\Lambda_G)$ is a one-sided shift space by Proposition 1.0.3. $\square$

Clearly every edge shift is a sofic shift, and since the class of sofic shifts is closed under conjugacy (cf. Corollary 3.2.2 in [10]), it follows that every topological Markov chain is a sofic shift. On the other hand not every sofic shift is a topological Markov chain (cf. Example 1.2.4 in [10]). We will return to the sofic shifts in Chapter 5.

Notes

Almost all the material covered in Chapter 1 is taken from [10] and adapted to one-sided shift spaces.

Chapter 2

C^* -algebras associated with one-sided shift spaces

In this chapter we will construct the C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ associated to a one-sided shift space Λ .

As described in the preface, we will do this by first associating a Hilbert bimodule to every one-sided shift space, and then to that associate the C^* -algebra Pimsner has associated to every Hilbert bimodule.

2.1 Pimsner algebras

In this section we first sum up the definition and some of the fundamental properties of the Pimsner algebras as described in [22]. We remark that the C^* -algebra we denote by $\mathcal{O}_\mathcal{H}$ is the C^* -algebra Pimsner denotes by $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_\mathcal{H}$ and calls the augmented C^* -algebra associated with $\mathcal{H}$.

Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a C^* -algebra and $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$. That is let $\mathcal{H}$ be a right Hilbert $\mathcal{X}$ -module and let $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H})$ be an isometric $*$ -homomorphism, where $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H})$ is the set of adjointable operators on $\mathcal{H}$.

We shall for each $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ by $\mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$ denote the n -fold tensor product of the module $\mathcal{H}$ with itself over the $*$ -homomorphism ϕ with the convention that $\mathcal{H}^{\otimes 0} = \mathcal{X}$. We then let $\mathfrak{H}_+ = \bigoplus_{n=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$, and we define for each $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ an operator $T_\xi \in \mathcal{L}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ by setting $T_\xi(\mu) = \xi \otimes \mu \in \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n+1}$ for each elementary tensor $\mu \in \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$.

For each $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $T \in \mathcal{L}(\bigoplus_{n=0}^k \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n})$ and $(\xi_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}_0} \in \mathfrak{H}_+$ we let

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_k(T)(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots) &= ((T(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_k))_0, (T(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_k))_1, \\ &\quad \dots, (T(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_k))_k, 0, 0, \dots) \end{aligned}$$

We let $\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ be the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{L}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ generated by $\psi_k(\mathcal{L}(\bigoplus_{n=0}^k \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}))$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, and we let $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ be the multiplier algebra of $\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ identified with all operators $T \in \mathcal{L}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ that satisfy $T\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+) \subseteq \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ and

$\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)T \subseteq \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$. It is easy to check that $T_\xi \in \mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$. Let $\pi : \mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)/\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ be the quotient map, and set $S_\xi = \pi(T_\xi)$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.

Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $T \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}^{\otimes k})$. We then define an operator $\iota_k(T)$ on $\mathfrak{H}_+$ by setting $\iota_k(T)(\xi) = 0$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$ with $n < k$, and

$$\iota_k(T)(\xi_1 \otimes \xi_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_k \otimes \xi_{k+1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_n) =$$

$$T(\xi_1 \otimes \xi_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_k) \otimes \xi_{k+1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_n$$

for every $n \geq k$ and every $\xi_1 \otimes \xi_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_k \otimes \xi_{k+1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_n \in \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$.

It is easy to check that ι_k is a $*$ -homomorphism and that $\iota_k(T) \in \mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+) \setminus \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$. So $\pi \circ \iota_k$ is a $*$ -monomorphism from $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}^{\otimes k})$ to $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)/\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$. We denote $\pi \circ \iota_k$ by $\iota^{(k)}$ and $\pi \circ \iota_1 \circ \phi$ by ι .

We define the Toeplitz algebra $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{H}}$ of the Hilbert bimodule $\mathcal{H}$ to be the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ generated by the operators T_ξ , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and $\iota_1 \circ \phi(\mathcal{X})$, and we define the Pimsner algebra $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ to be the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{H}_+)/\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{H}_+)$ generated by the operators S_ξ , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and $\iota(\mathcal{X})$.

Remark 2.1.1. Every isomorphism of the Hilbert bimodule $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ - these are precisely the unitaries in $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H})$ that commute with $\phi(X)$, for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ - gives rise to an automorphism of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$. In particular, every C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ comes equipped with an action $(\alpha_z)_{z \in \mathbb{T}}$ of the circle $\mathbb{T}$ as automorphism of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ such that $\alpha_z(S_\xi) = zS_\xi$ for every $z \in \mathbb{T}$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.

Proposition 2.1.2. Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a C^* -algebra and $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$. The elements in $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ satisfy the following relations:

- a) $\alpha S_\xi + \beta S_\zeta = S_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- b) $S_\xi^* S_\zeta = \iota(\langle \xi, \zeta \rangle)$ for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- c) $S_{\zeta_1} \cdots S_{\zeta_n} S_{\xi_n}^* \cdots S_{\xi_1}^* = \iota^{(n)}((\zeta_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes \zeta_n) \otimes (\xi_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_n)^*)$ for every $\zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n, \xi_1, \dots, \xi_n \in \mathcal{H}$.
- d) $S_\xi \iota(X) = S_{\xi X}$ and $\iota(X) S_\xi = S_{\phi(X)\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $X \in \mathcal{X}$.
- e) $\iota^{(1)}(T) S_\xi = S_{T(\xi)}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $T \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H})$.

Theorem 2.1.3. Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a C^* -algebra and $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$. If $\mathcal{Y}$ is a C^* -algebra, $\psi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is a $*$ -homomorphism and there exist elements $\tilde{T}_\xi \in \mathcal{Y}$, $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ such that:

- a) $\alpha \tilde{T}_\xi + \beta \tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- b) $\tilde{T}_\xi \psi(X) = \tilde{T}_{\xi X}$ and $\psi(X) \tilde{T}_\xi = \tilde{T}_{\phi(X)\xi}$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.

$$c) \tilde{T}_\xi^* \tilde{T}_\zeta = \psi(\langle \xi, \zeta \rangle) \text{ for every } \xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}.$$

then there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ to $\mathcal{Y}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(\iota_1(\phi(X))) = \psi(X)$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, and $\psi(T_\xi) = \tilde{T}_\xi$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.

Definition 2.1.4. For a C^* -algebra $\mathcal{X}$ and a Hilbert bimodule $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ over $\mathcal{X}$ we let $\mathcal{I} = \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{H}))$.

Lemma 2.1.5. Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a C^* -algebra and $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$. If $\mathcal{Y}$ is a C^* -algebra, $\psi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is a $*$ -homomorphism and there exist elements $\tilde{T}_\xi \in \mathcal{Y}$, $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ such that:

- a) $\alpha \tilde{T}_\xi + \beta \tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- b) $\tilde{T}_\xi \psi(X) = \tilde{T}_{\xi X}$ and $\psi(X) \tilde{T}_\xi = \tilde{T}_{\phi(X)\xi}$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.
- c) $\tilde{T}_\xi^* \tilde{T}_\zeta = \psi(\langle \xi, \zeta \rangle)$ for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.

then for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ the map

$$(\xi_1 \otimes \xi_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_n) \otimes (\zeta_1 \otimes \zeta_2 \otimes \cdots \otimes \zeta_n)^* \mapsto \tilde{T}_{\xi_1} \tilde{T}_{\xi_2} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\xi_n} \tilde{T}_{\zeta_n}^* \cdots \tilde{T}_{\zeta_2}^* \tilde{T}_{\zeta_1}^*$$

extends to a $*$ -homomorphism $\psi^{(n)}$ from $\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{H}^{\otimes n})$ to $\mathcal{Y}$.

Theorem 2.1.6. Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a C^* -algebra and $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$. If $\mathcal{Y}$ is a C^* -algebra, $\psi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is a $*$ -homomorphism and there exist elements $\tilde{T}_\xi \in \mathcal{Y}$, $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ such that:

- a) $\alpha \tilde{T}_\xi + \beta \tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- b) $\tilde{T}_\xi \psi(X) = \tilde{T}_{\xi X}$ and $\psi(X) \tilde{T}_\xi = \tilde{T}_{\phi(X)\xi}$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.
- c) $\tilde{T}_\xi^* \tilde{T}_\zeta = \psi(\langle \xi, \zeta \rangle)$ for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.
- d) $\psi^{(1)}\phi(X) = \psi(X)$ for every $X \in \mathcal{I}$.

then there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ to $\mathcal{Y}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(\iota(X)) = \psi(X)$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, and $\tilde{\psi}(S_\xi) = \tilde{T}_\xi$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.

2.2 Hilbert bimodules associated with one-sided shift spaces

We will now define the Hilbert bimodule that we associate to a one-sided shift space. As a matter of facts we will to each one-sided shift space Λ associate two Hilbert bimodules $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$. We will in Theorem 2.5.2 show that

$\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ are canonical isomorphic. The reason that we associate two Hilbert bimodules is that sometimes it is more convenient to work with $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ (cf. Section 3.1, 4.3 and 4.4) and other times it is more convenient to work with $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ (cf. Section 4.1).

We start by defining the C^* -algebra which $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ is a Hilbert bimodule over and the C^* -algebra which $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ is a Hilbert bimodule over.

Definition 2.2.1. For every one-sided shift space Λ we let $\mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ be the abelian C^* -algebra of all bounded functions on Λ , $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ generated by $1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Then we define $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$:

Definition 2.2.2. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. For every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ let $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a$ be the ideal in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ generated by $1_{\sigma(C(a))}$ and let $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_a$ be the ideal in $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ generated by $1_{\sigma(C(a))}$. Let $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ be the right Hilbert $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ -module

$$\bigoplus_{i \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_i,$$

and let $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ be the right Hilbert $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ -module

$$\bigoplus_{i \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_i.$$

Now we only got to define ϕ and ϕ' .

Proposition 2.2.3. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space and let $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Define a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\lambda}_a : \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda) \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ by letting

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)(x) = \begin{cases} f(ax) & \text{if } ax \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } ax \notin \Lambda \end{cases}$$

for every $f \in \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ and every $x \in \Lambda$.

Then $\tilde{\lambda}_a(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_a(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_a$.

Proof. Let $f \in \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ and $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. For every $x \in \Lambda$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) (x) &= \begin{cases} 1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}(ax) & \text{if } ax \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } ax \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mu ax \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } \mu ax \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\ &= 1_{\sigma^{|\mu a|}(C(\mu a))}(x). \end{aligned}$$

So $\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) = 1_{\sigma^{|\mu a|}(C(\mu a))} \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a$, since $1_{\sigma^{|\mu a|}(C(\mu a))} \leq 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$. Hence $\tilde{\lambda}_a(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a$, since $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$. For every $x \in \Lambda$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) (x) &= \begin{cases} 1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))(ax)} & \text{if } ax \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } ax \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a = \nu_1, x_1 = \nu_2, \dots, x_{|\nu|-1} = \nu_{|\nu|}, \mu(x_{|\nu|}, x_{|\nu|+1}, \dots), ax \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = 0$$

if $a \neq \nu_1$, and

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = 1_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|}) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))))} 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$$

if $a = \nu_1$. Hence $\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) \in \tilde{D}_a$. So $\tilde{\lambda}_a(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_a$, since $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. $\square$

Proposition 2.2.4. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Let for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ and every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$,*

$$\phi(f)((f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}) = (\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}.$$

Then $\phi : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}_\Lambda)$ is an isometric $*$ -homomorphism.

Proof. It is easy to check that $\phi(f) \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}_\Lambda)$ for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$, and that ϕ is a $*$ -homomorphism.

Let $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$. For every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \|\phi(f)((f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}})\|^2 &= \|(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}\|^2 \\ &= \|\langle (\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \rangle\| \\ &= \left\| \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} f_a^* \tilde{\lambda}_a(f^*) \tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a \right\| \\ &= \left\| \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{\lambda}_a(f^* f) f_a^* f_a \right\| \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \|\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)\|^2 f_a^* f_a \right\| \\ &\leq \|f\|^2 \left\| \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} f_a^* f_a \right\| \\ &= \|f\|^2 \|(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

So $\|\phi(f)\| \leq \|f\|$.

Given $\epsilon > 0$. Choose $x \in \Lambda$ such that $|f(x)| \geq \|f\| - \epsilon$. Let for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, ξ_a be the element $(f_{a'})_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ where $f_a = 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$ and $f_{a'} = 0$ for $a' \neq a$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} \left(|\tilde{\lambda}_{x_1}(f)|^2 1_{\sigma(C(x_1))} \right) (x_2, x_3, \dots) &= |f(x)|^2 \\ &\geq (\|f\| - \epsilon)^2, \end{aligned}$$

we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\phi(f)\xi_{x_1}\|^2 &= \|\langle \phi(f)\xi_{x_1}, \phi(f)\xi_{x_1} \rangle\| \\ &= \left\| \left(\tilde{\lambda}_{x_1}(f) 1_{\sigma(C(x_1))} \right)^* \tilde{\lambda}_{x_1}(f) 1_{\sigma(C(x_1))} \right\| \\ &= \left\| |\tilde{\lambda}_{x_1}(f)|^2 1_{\sigma(C(x_1))} \right\| \\ &\geq (\|f\| - \epsilon)^2, \end{aligned}$$

and thus $\|\phi(f)\| \geq \|f\| - \epsilon$. So $\|\phi(f)\| = \|f\|$. Hence ϕ is isometric. $\square$

In exactly the same way we proved Proposition 2.2.4, we can prove the following Proposition.

Proposition 2.2.5. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Let for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ and every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$,*

$$\phi'(f)((f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}) = (\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}.$$

Then $\phi' : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda)$ is an isometric $$ -homomorphism.*

Hence by Proposition 2.2.4, $(\mathcal{H}_\Lambda, \phi)$ is a Hilbert bimodule over $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$, and by Proposition 2.2.5, $(\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda, \phi')$ as a Hilbert bimodule over $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.

Since $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is a C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, we can regard $(\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda, \phi')$ as a Hilbert bimodule over $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ and if we do that, then $(\mathcal{H}_\Lambda, \phi)$ is a submodule of $(\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda, \phi')$.

2.3 $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$

We will now take a closer look at $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$. We begin with $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$.

We first show that $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ is unital.

Lemma 2.3.1. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space and let 1 be the unit of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$. Then $\iota(1)$ is a unit for $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$.*

Proof. It follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that $S_\xi \iota(1) = S_{\xi_1} = S_\xi$, and $\iota(1) S_\xi = S_{\phi'(1)\xi} = S_\xi$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$. Since we also have that $\iota(1)\iota(f) = \iota(f)\iota(1) = \iota(f)$ for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ is generated by $S_\xi, \xi \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ and $\iota(f), f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, we have that $\iota(1)$ is a unit for $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$. $\square$

Definition 2.3.2. Let Λ be a one-sided shift. For every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ let ξ_a be the element $(f_{a'})_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ where $f_a = 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$ and $f_{a'} = 0$ for $a' \neq a$, and let for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, S_μ be the product $S_{\xi_{\mu_1}} S_{\xi_{\mu_2}} \cdots S_{\xi_{\mu_{|\mu|}}} \in \mathcal{O}_{H'_\Lambda}$ with the convention that $S_\emptyset = I$.

Lemma 2.3.3. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Let 1 be the unit of $\tilde{D}_\Lambda$, and I the unit of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda)$. Then

$$\iota(1) = \iota^{(1)}(I) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^*$$

is the unit of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$.

Proof. It is easy to check that

$$\phi'(1) = I = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \xi_a \otimes \xi_a^*.$$

So it follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that

$$\iota(1) = \iota^{(1)}(I) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^*,$$

and from Lemma 2.3.1 we know that $\iota(1)$ is the unit of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$. □

Lemma 2.3.4. Let Λ be a one-sided shift. Then

$$\iota \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Proof. Since

$$\begin{aligned} S_a^* S_a &= S_{\xi_a}^* S_{\xi_a} \\ &= \iota(\langle \xi_a, \xi_a \rangle) \\ &= \iota(1_{\sigma(C(a))}), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} S_a^* \iota \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|}(C(\mu'))} \right) S_a &= S_{\xi_a}^* S_{\phi' \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|}(C(\mu'))} \right) \xi_a} \\ &= S_{\xi_a}^* S_{\xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|}(C(\mu'))} \right)} \\ &= S_{\xi_a}^* S_{\xi_a} \iota \left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|}(C(\mu'))} \right) \right) \\ &= \iota \left(1_{\sigma(C(a))} \tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|}(C(\mu'))} \right) \right) \\ &= \iota \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu'|} a | (C(\mu' a))} \right) \end{aligned}$$

for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ and every $\mu' \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, we have that

$$S_{\mu'}^* S_{\mu'} = \iota \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right)$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

It is easy to check that for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}$ is

$$\phi'(f) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f) \otimes \xi_a^*.$$

Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Then as proved in the proof of Proposition 2.2.3

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{(C_{\nu}) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = 0$$

if $a \neq \nu_1$, and

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = 1_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$$

if $a = \nu_1$.

So

$$\begin{aligned} \iota \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) &= \iota^{(1)} \left(\phi' \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) \right) \\ &= \iota^{(1)} \left(\xi_{\nu_1} 1_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \otimes \xi_{\nu_1}^* \right) \\ &= S_{\xi_{\nu_1}} 1_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} S_{\xi_{\nu_1}}^* \\ &= S_{\nu_1} 1_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} S_{\nu_1}^*. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\iota \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{\nu}^*$$

for all $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. $\square$

Proposition 2.3.5. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}}$ is generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.*

Proof. $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}}$ is by definition generated by S_{ξ} , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}$ and $\iota(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda})$.

First notice that $\iota(1) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^*$ is in the C^* -algebra generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Since

$$\iota \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{\nu}^*$$

for all $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, and $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}$ is generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, we have that $\iota(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda})$ is in the C^* -algebra generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.

Let $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}$. By Proposition 2.1.2 we have that $S_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \iota(f_a)$, and thus $S_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}$ is in the C^* -algebra generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Hence $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}}$ is generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. $\square$

Now we turn to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$.

In the same way we proved Lemma 2.3.1, we can prove that $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ is unital.

Definition 2.3.6. Let Λ be a one-sided shift. For every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ let ξ_a be the element $(f_{a'})_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ where $f_a = 1_{\sigma(U_a)}$ and $f_{a'} = 0$ for $a' \neq a$, and let for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, S_μ be the product $S_{\xi_{\mu_1}} S_{\xi_{\mu_2}} \cdots S_{\xi_{\mu_{|\mu|}}} \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ with the convention that $S_\emptyset = I$.

In exactly the same way that we proved Lemma 2.3.3, we can prove the following Lemma:

Lemma 2.3.7. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Let 1 be the unit of $\tilde{A}_\Lambda$ and I the unit of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H}_\Lambda)$. Then

$$\iota(1) = \iota^{(1)}(I) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^*$$

is the unit of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$.

The following Lemma and Proposition can be proved in a similar way that Lemma 2.3.4 and Proposition 2.3.5 were proved, just a little bit simpler.

Lemma 2.3.8. Let Λ be a one-sided shift. Then

$$\iota\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}\right) = S_\mu^* S_\mu$$

for all $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Proposition 2.3.9. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ is generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.

2.4 The structure of C^* -algebras generated by partial isometries

We have now established that both $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ are unital C^* -algebras generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ that satisfy

$$\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* = I.$$

We will show that there exists a $*$ -isomorphism between $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ that sends S_a to S_a for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. But before we do that, we will take a closer look at unital C^* -algebras generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ that satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* &= I, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* &= S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu &= S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Lemma 2.4.1. *Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a unital C^* -algebra and $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n \in \mathcal{X}$ be projections. Then the following are equivalent:*

- a) $P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n$ are mutually orthogonal.
- b) $P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n$ is a projection.
- c) $P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n \leq I$.

Proof. a) $\Rightarrow$ b): Clearly

$$(P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n)^* = P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n$$

and since $P_i P_j = 0$ for $i \neq j$,

$$\begin{aligned} (P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n)(P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n) &= P_1^2 + P_2^2 + \cdots + P_n^2 \\ &= P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n. \end{aligned}$$

So $P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n$ is a projection.

b) $\Rightarrow$ c): Since $P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n$ is a projection, we just have to show that $P \leq I$ for every projection, and this follows from the fact that $I - P$ is a projection and hence positive.

c) $\Rightarrow$ a): For every $i \neq j$ we have that

$$P_i + P_j \leq P_1 + P_2 + \cdots + P_n \leq I$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned} P_i + P_i P_j P_i &= P_i(P_i + P_j)P_i \\ &\leq P_i I P_i \\ &= P_i, \end{aligned}$$

so $(P_i P_j)(P_i P_j)^* = P_i P_j P_i = 0$, and hence $P_i P_j = 0$. $\square$

Let $\mathfrak{A}$ be an alphabet. In the following we let $\mathcal{O}$ be a unital C^* -algebra generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, such that

$$\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* = I, \quad (2.1)$$

$$S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* = S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu, \quad (2.2)$$

$$S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu = S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu, \quad (2.3)$$

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Lemma 2.4.2. *For every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, S_μ is a partial isometry.*

Proof. We will prove the Lemma by induction over the length of $|\mu|$. If $|\mu| = 1$, then S_μ is a partial isometry by definition. Assume now that S_ν is a partial isometry and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\nu a} S_{\nu a}^* S_{\nu a} &= S_\nu S_a S_a^* S_\nu^* S_\nu S_a \\ &= S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\nu S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= S_\nu S_a \\ &= S_{\nu a}. \end{aligned}$$

So $S_{\nu a}$ is a partial isometry. Hence S_μ is a partial isometry for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. $\square$

For $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ we set $A_\mu = S_\mu^* S_\mu$. We notice that since $\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* = I$ it follows from Lemma 2.4.1 that $S_a S_a^* S_b S_b^* = 0$ for $a \neq b$.

Lemma 2.4.3. *Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. If $S_\mu^* S_\nu \neq 0$, then*

- a) $\mu = \nu$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu = A_\mu$, if $|\mu| = |\nu|$,
- b) $\mu = \nu \mu'$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu = A_\mu S_{\nu'}^*$, for some $\mu' \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, if $|\mu| > |\nu|$,
- c) $\nu = \mu \nu'$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu = S_{\nu'} A_\nu$ for some $\nu' \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, if $|\mu| < |\nu|$.

Proof. We will prove a) by induction over the length of μ and ν . If the length is 1 and $\mu \neq \nu$, then

$$\begin{aligned} S_\mu^* S_\nu &= S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\mu^* S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\nu \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

since $S_\mu S_\mu^* S_\nu S_\nu^* = 0$. So since $S_\mu^* S_\nu \neq 0$, we have that $\mu = \nu$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu = A_\mu$.

Now assume that we have proved a) in case $|\mu| = |\nu| = n$, and assume that $|\mu'| = |\nu'| = n + 1$ and $S_{\mu'}^* S_{\nu'} \neq 0$. Set $\mu = (\mu'_1, \dots, \mu'_n)$ and $\nu = (\nu'_1, \dots, \nu'_n)$. Then $S_\mu^* S_\nu \neq 0$, so $\mu = \nu$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\neq S_{\mu'}^* S_{\nu'} \\ &= S_{\mu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\mu'} S_{\nu'} S_{\nu'_{n+1}} \\ &= S_{\mu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\mu'_{n+1}} S_{\mu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\mu'} S_{\nu'} S_{\nu'_{n+1}} S_{\nu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\nu'_{n+1}} \\ &= S_{\mu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\mu'_{n+1}} S_{\mu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\nu'_{n+1}} S_{\nu'_{n+1}}^* S_{\mu'} S_{\nu'} S_{\nu'_{n+1}}, \end{aligned}$$

we have that $\mu'_{n+1} = \nu'_{n+1}$, and hence $\mu' = \nu'$. So a) is true.

If $|\mu| > |\nu|$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu \neq 0$, then $\mu = \nu \mu'$ by a), and

$$\begin{aligned} S_\mu^* S_\nu &= S_{\mu'}^* S_{\nu'} S_\nu \\ &= S_{\mu'}^* S_{\mu'} S_{\mu'}^* S_{\nu'} S_\nu \\ &= S_{\mu'}^* S_{\nu'} S_\nu S_{\mu'} S_{\mu'}^* \\ &= A_\mu S_{\mu'}^*. \end{aligned}$$

So b) is true.

If $|\mu| < |\nu|$ and $S_\mu^* S_\nu \neq 0$, then $\nu = \mu\nu'$ by a), and

$$\begin{aligned} S_\mu^* S_\nu &= S_\mu^* S_\mu S_{\nu'} \\ &= S_\mu^* S_\mu S_{\nu'} S_{\nu'}^* S_{\nu'} \\ &= S_{\nu'} S_{\nu'}^* S_\mu^* S_\mu S_{\nu'} \\ &= S_{\nu'} A_\nu. \end{aligned}$$

so c) is true. $\square$

For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}$ generated by A_μ , $\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. Since $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$ is generated by a finite number of mutually commuting projection, there exist a finite number of mutually orthogonal minimal projections E_i^l , $i = 1, \dots, m(l)$, such that $(E_i^l)_{i=1, \dots, m(l)}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$.

We have that $\overline{\bigcup_{l \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})}$ is the C^* -algebra generated by A_μ , $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. We denoted this C^* -algebra by $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$. Since $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$ is finite dimensional and $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}) \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{l+1}(\mathcal{O})$ for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$ is an AF-algebra.

For $1 \leq k \leq l$ we denote by $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}$ generated by elements of the form $S_\mu A S_\nu^*$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, $A \in \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$.

Lemma 2.4.4. *For $1 \leq k \leq l$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ we have that the following conditions are equivalent:*

- a) $S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \neq 0$
- b) $A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu \neq 0$
- c) $A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu = E_i^l$

Proof. a) $\Leftrightarrow$ b): Since

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* = S_\mu A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu S_\nu^*,$$

and

$$A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu = S_\mu^* S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_\nu,$$

we have that

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \neq 0 \Leftrightarrow A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu \neq 0.$$

b) $\Rightarrow$ c): Since $A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu E_i^l = A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu$, we have that $A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu \leq E_i^l$, and since E_i^l is a minimal projection in $\mathcal{A}_l$ we have that

$$A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu \neq 0 \Rightarrow A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu = E_i^l.$$

c) $\Rightarrow$ b): Obvious, since $E_i^l \neq 0$. $\square$

Lemma 2.4.5. *Let $l \geq k \geq 1$. For $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ let*

$$Z_k^l(i) = \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}}) \mid A_\mu E_i^l \neq 0\}.$$

Then

a) $S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \neq 0$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and $\mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)$.

b) For $i, i' \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, $\mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)$ and $\mu', \nu' \in Z_k^l(i')$ is

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_{\mu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* = \begin{cases} S_\mu E_i^l S_{\nu'}^* & \text{if } \nu = \mu' \text{ and } i = i' \\ 0 & \text{if } \nu \neq \mu' \text{ or } i \neq i'. \end{cases}$$

c) $(S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^*)^* = S_\nu E_i^l S_\mu^*$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and $\mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)$.

d) $\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})$.

Proof. a): Since $A_\mu E_i^l A_\mu = A_\mu E_i^l \neq 0$ and $A_\nu E_i^l A_\nu = A_\nu E_i^l \neq 0$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu &= A_\mu E_i^l A_\mu A_\nu E_i^l A_\nu \\ &= E_i^l \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 2.4.4. Hence $S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \neq 0$ also by Lemma 2.4.4.

b): By Lemma 2.4.3

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_{\mu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* = \begin{cases} S_\mu E_i^l A_\nu E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* & \text{if } \nu = \mu' \\ 0 & \text{if } \nu \neq \mu'. \end{cases}$$

Since $S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \neq 0$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} S_\mu E_i^l A_\nu &= S_\mu A_\mu E_i^l A_\nu \\ &= S_\mu E_i^l \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 2.4.4. So

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_{\mu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* = \begin{cases} S_\mu E_i^l E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* & \text{if } \nu = \mu' \\ 0 & \text{if } \nu \neq \mu'. \end{cases}$$

Hence

$$S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_{\mu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* = \begin{cases} S_\mu E_i^l S_{\nu'}^* & \text{if } \nu = \mu' \text{ and } i = i' \\ 0 & \text{if } \nu \neq \mu' \text{ or } i \neq i'. \end{cases}$$

c): Obviously.

d): Clearly

$$\text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{X})$$

and

$$S_\mu AS_\nu^* \in \text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $A \in \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$. So if

$$\text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is a C^* -algebra, it is equal to $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})$.

Naturally

$$\text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is closed under addition and conjugation, and since $S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* S_\alpha E_j^l S_\beta^*$ is equal to $S_\mu E_i^l S_\beta^*$ or 0, it is also closed under multiplication; and since

$$\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is finite,

$$\text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is finite dimensional and hence closed. So

$$\text{span}\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is a C^* -algebra.

Since

$$S_{\mu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* (S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^*) S_{\nu'} E_{i'}^l S_{\nu'}^* = \begin{cases} S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* & \text{if } \mu' = \mu, \nu' = \nu, i' = i \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases}$$

we have that

$$\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$$

is linear independent, so $\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})$. $\square$

For every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ denote by $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}$ generated by $S_\mu AS_\nu^*$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$ and denote by $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}$ generated by $S_\mu AS_\nu^*$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\mu| = |\nu|$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$. Then

$$\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}) = \overline{\bigcup_{k \leq l} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})}$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}) = \overline{\bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O})} = \overline{\bigcup_{1 \leq k \leq l} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})}.$$

Since $S_\mu AS_\nu^* = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{\mu a} S_a^* A S_{\nu a} S_{\nu a}^*$ for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $A \in \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$, we have that $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}_{k+1}^{l+1}(\mathcal{O})$ and $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}_{k+1}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ for every $1 \leq k \leq l$.

Proposition 2.4.6. *Let $\mathcal{O}$ be unital C^* -algebras generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* &= I, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* &= S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu &= S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$; and let $\mathcal{O}'$ be a unital C^* -algebra generated by partial isometries T_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} T_a T_a^* &= I, \\ T_\mu^* T_\mu T_\nu T_\nu^* &= T_\nu T_\nu^* T_\mu^* T_\mu, \\ T_\mu^* T_\mu T_\nu^* T_\nu &= T_\nu^* T_\nu T_\mu^* T_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

where $T_\mu = T_{\mu_1} \cdots T_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $T_\nu = T_{\nu_1} \cdots T_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

If $\phi : \mathcal{O} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}'$ is a $*$ -homomorphism such that $\phi(S_a) = T_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ and $\phi|_{\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$ to $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O}')$, then $\phi|_{\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ to $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}')$.

Proof. Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $\phi|_{\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism between $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$ and $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}')$, we have that if E_i^l , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ are mutually orthogonal minimal projections in $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$ such that $(E_i^l)_{i=1,2,\dots,m(l)}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$, then $\phi(E_i^l)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ are mutually orthogonal minimal projections in $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}')$ such that $(\phi(E_i^l))_{i=1,2,\dots,m(l)}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}')$.

Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. Since $\phi|_{\mathcal{A}_k(\mathcal{O})}$ is injective, we have that $\phi(A_\mu E_i^l) = 0$ if and only if $A_\mu E_i^l = 0$ for $\mu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$. Thus by Lemma 2.4.5 we have that $\{S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^* \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})$, and $\{\phi(S_\mu E_i^l S_\nu^*) \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}, \mu, \nu \in Z_k^l(i)\}$ is a basis for $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}')$. Hence $\phi|_{\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism, and since $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}) = \overline{\bigcup_{1 \leq k \leq l} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O})}$ it follows that $\phi|_{\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ to $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}')$. $\square$

We denote by $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$ the $*$ -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}$ generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Then by Lemma 2.4.3 we have that every element $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$ can be written as a finite sum

$$\sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X_{-\nu} S_\nu^* + X_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} S_\mu X_\mu$$

with $X_{-\nu}, X_\mu, X_0 \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$.

Proposition 2.4.7. *Let $\mathcal{O}$ be unital C^* -algebras generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* &= I, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* &= S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu &= S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. If there exists an action $(\alpha_z)_{z \in \mathbb{T}}$ of the circle $\mathbb{T}$ as automorphism of $\mathcal{O}$ such that the map $z \mapsto \alpha_z(X)$ is continuous for every $X \in \mathcal{O}$ and such that $\alpha_z(S_a) = z S_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, then there exists a faithful, continuous, linear map $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}} : \mathcal{O} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = X$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(S_\nu X) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X S_\nu^*) = 0$ for $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$.

Proof. Let dz be the normalized Haar measure on $\mathbb{T}$. Define $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}} : \mathcal{O} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ by

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(X) dz$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{O}$.

It is clear that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}$ is linear, and since

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X)\| &= \left\| \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(X) dz \right\| \\ &\leq \int_{\mathbb{T}} \|\alpha_z(X)\| dz \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \|X\| dz \\ &= \|X\| \end{aligned}$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{O}$, $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}$ is continuous.

Since $\alpha_z(S_\mu A S_\nu^*) = S_\mu A S_\nu^*$ for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\mu| = |\nu|$, $A \in \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$ and $z \in \mathbb{T}$, and α_z is continuous, we have that $\alpha_z(X) = X$ for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ and every $z \in \mathbb{T}$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(X) dz \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} X dz \\ &= X, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(S_{\mu}X) &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(S_{\mu}X) dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} z^{|\mu|} S_{\mu}X dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} z^{|\mu|} dz S_{\mu}X \\
 &= 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(XS_{\mu}^*) &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(XS_{\mu}^*) dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} z^{-|\mu|} XS_{\mu}^* dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} z^{-|\mu|} dz XS_{\mu}^* \\
 &= 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^{\infty}(\mathcal{O})$ and every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\mu| \leq 1$. Since every element $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$ can be written as a finite sum

$$X = \sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X_{-\nu} S_{\nu}^* + X_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} S_{\mu} X_{\mu}$$

for some $X_{-\nu}, X_0, X_{\mu} \in \mathcal{F}^{\infty}(\mathcal{O})$, we get that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^{\infty}(\mathcal{O})$, and thus $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\mathcal{O}) = \mathcal{F}^{\infty}(\mathcal{O})$, since $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$ is dense in $\mathcal{O}$.

Assume that $X \in \mathcal{O}$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X^*X) = 0$. Let π be a faithful representation of $\mathcal{O}$ on a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= \langle \pi(\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X^*X))\xi, \xi \rangle \\
 &= \left\langle \pi \left(\int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(X^*X) dz \right) \xi, \xi \right\rangle \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \langle \pi(\alpha_z(X^*X))\xi, \xi \rangle dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \langle \pi(\alpha_z(X))\xi, \pi(\alpha_z(X))\xi \rangle dz \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \|\pi(\alpha_z(X))\xi\|^2 dz
 \end{aligned}$$

and thus $\pi(\alpha_z(X))\xi = 0$ for every $z \in \mathbb{T}$. Hence $X = 0$. So $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}$ is faithful. $\square$

2.5 $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}} \cong \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}}$

We will now show that $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}}$ is isomorphic to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}}$ for every one-sided shift space Λ .

Proposition 2.5.1. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift, $\mathcal{X}$ a C^* -algebra, $\psi : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ a $*$ -homomorphism and $S_a \in \mathcal{X}$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, partial isometries such that*

- a) $\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* = \psi(1)$,
- b) $S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* = S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu$,
- c) $S_\mu^* S_\mu = \psi\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}\right)$,

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} S_{\mu_2} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} S_{\nu_2} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$.

Then ψ extends to a $*$ -homomorphism from $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$, such that

$$\psi\left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{O}$ be the C^* -subalgebra of $\mathcal{X}$ generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Since $S_\mu^* S_\mu = \psi\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}\right)$ and $S_\nu^* S_\nu = \psi\left(1_{\sigma^{|\nu|}(C(\nu))}\right)$, we have that $S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu = S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu$ for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} S_a \psi(1) &= S_a S_a^* S_a \psi(1) \\ &= S_a \psi(1_{C(a)}) \psi(1) \\ &= S_a \psi(1_{C(a)}) \\ &= S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= S_a \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(1) S_a &= \psi(1) S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= \sum_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{a'} S_{a'}^* S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= S_a \end{aligned}$$

for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, $\psi(1)$ is a unit for $\mathcal{O}$. Hence $\mathcal{O}$ and S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, satisfy (2.1), (2.2) and (2.3).

For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$ denote by $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ generated by $1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$. Since $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$ is generated by a finite number of mutually commuting projections, there exists a finite number $m(l)$ of mutually disjoint minimal subsets $\mathcal{E}_i^l$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ of Λ such that $\{1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}\}$ is a basis for $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$.

Then $\psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ are mutually orthogonal minimal projections in $\mathcal{O}$ and $\text{span}\{\psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}\} = \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O})$. So by

Lemma 2.4.5 we have that for $1 \leq k \leq l$ are $S_\nu \psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) S_\nu^*$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ mutually orthogonal projections in $\mathcal{O}$.

For each $1 \leq k \leq l$ denote by $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^l$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. It is easy to check that

$$1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\mathcal{E}_i^l)}, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda), i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$$

are mutually orthogonal projections in $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^l$, and since

$$\begin{aligned} 1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} = 0 &\Rightarrow 1_{\sigma^{|\nu|}(C(\nu))} 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow S_\nu^* S_\nu \psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow S_\nu \psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) S_\nu^* = 0, \end{aligned}$$

there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\psi_k^l : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^l \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ such that $\psi_k^l \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} \right) = S_\nu \psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) S_\nu^*$ for every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and hence $\psi_k^l \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$ for every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

For every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ denote by $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k$ the C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k = \bigcup_{l \geq k} \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^l$. Let ι_k^l denote the inclusion of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^l$ into $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k^{l+1}$. Since $\psi_k^{l+1} \circ \iota_k^l = \psi_k^l$ for every $l \geq k$, the ψ_k^l 's induce a $*$ -homomorphism $\psi_k : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ such that $\psi_k \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$ for every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Since

$$C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))) = \bigcup_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} C(\nu a) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu a|}(C(\mu a)))$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{k+1}$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and the inclusion ι_k of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k$ into $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{k+1}$ is given by

$$\iota_k \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} 1_{C(\nu a) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu a|}(C(\mu a)))}.$$

Hence $\psi_{k+1} \circ \iota_k = \psi_k$ and since $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda = \overline{\bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_k}$, the ψ_k 's induce a $*$ -homomorphism $\psi : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$\psi \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. $\square$

Theorem 2.5.2. *For every one-sided shift space Λ there exists an $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ that sends S_a to S_a for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.*

Proof. Let $\rho : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ be the inclusion, $\rho' = \iota \circ \rho$ and let $\tilde{T}_\xi = S_\xi \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ (here we regard $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ as a subset of $\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda'}$). Then by Proposition 2.1.2 we have that

- a) $\alpha\tilde{T}_\xi + \beta\tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.
- b) $\tilde{T}_\xi \rho'(a) = \tilde{T}_{\xi_a}$ and $\rho'(a)\tilde{T}_\xi = \tilde{T}_{\phi(a)\xi}$ for every $a \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.
- c) $\tilde{T}_\xi^* \tilde{T}_\zeta = \rho'(\langle \xi, \zeta \rangle)$ for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.
- d) $\rho'^{(1)}\phi(a) = \rho'(a)$ for every $a \in \mathcal{I}$.

So it follows from Theorem 2.1.6 that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\rho}'$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ sending $S_a = S_{\xi_a}$ to $\tilde{T}_{\xi_a} = S_{\xi_a} = S_a \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$.

From Lemma 2.3.8 we know that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\iota : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ such that

$$\iota \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) = S_\mu^* S_\mu,$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, and by Lemma 2.3.7 we know that $\iota(1) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^*$. It is easy to check that $\iota_{|\nu|}((\xi_{\nu_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_{\nu_{|\nu|}}) \otimes ((\xi_{\nu_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_{\nu_{|\nu|}})^*))$ commutes with $\iota_1 \left(\phi \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \right)$ in $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$, and hence $S_\nu S_\nu^* = \pi(\iota_{|\nu|}((\xi_{\nu_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_{\nu_{|\nu|}}) \otimes ((\xi_{\nu_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes \xi_{\nu_{|\nu|}})^*))$ commutes with $S_\mu^* S_\mu = \pi \left(\iota_1 \left(\phi \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \right) \right)$ in $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. So by Proposition 2.5.1 ι extends to a $*$ -homomorphism $\psi : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ such that

$$\psi \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^*$$

for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Let for each $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$,

$$\tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \psi(f_a) \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}.$$

It is easy to check that $\alpha\tilde{T}_\xi + \beta\tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$, and that $\tilde{T}_\xi \psi(f) = \tilde{T}_{\xi f}$ for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ and every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$. By Proposition 2.1.2 we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) S_{\xi_a} &= \iota \left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} \right) S_{\xi_a} \\ &= S_{\xi_a} \iota \left(\lambda_a(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}) \right) \\ &= S_{\xi_a} \psi \left(\lambda_a(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. Assume now that $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $|\nu| \geq 1$. Then

$$\psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) S_{\xi_a} = S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{\nu}^* S_{\xi_a}.$$

If $a \neq \nu_1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\nu_1}^* S_{\xi_a} &= S_{\nu_1}^* S_{\nu_1} S_{\nu_1}^* S_a S_a^* S_a \\ &= S_{\nu_1}^* \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu_1)} \right) \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(a)} \right) S_a \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

and hence $S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{\nu}^* S_{\xi_a} = 0$, and if $a = \nu_1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{\nu}^* S_{\xi_a} &= S_{\nu_1} \left(S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^* \right) (S_{\nu_1}^* S_{\nu_1}) \\ &= S_{\nu_1} \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C((\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{\sigma(C(\nu_1))} \right) \\ &= S_{\nu_1} \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{\sigma(C(\nu_1))} \right) \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C((\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \\ &= S_{\nu_1} (S_{\nu_1}^* S_{\nu_1}) \left(S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^* \right) \\ &= S_{\nu_1} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^* \\ &= S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^*. \end{aligned}$$

As proved in the proof of Proposition 2.2.3

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) = 0$$

if $a \neq \nu_1$, and

$$\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) = \mathbf{1}_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \mathbf{1}_{\sigma(C(a))}$$

if $a = \nu_1$. So

$$S_{\xi_a} \psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \right) = 0$$

if $a \neq \nu_1$, and

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\xi_a} \psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \right) &= S_{\xi_a} \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{\sigma(C(a))} \right) \psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C((\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})) \cap \sigma^{1-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \\ &= S_a S_a^* S_a S_{(\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^* \\ &= S_{\nu} S_{\mu}^* S_{\mu} S_{(\nu_2, \nu_3, \dots, \nu_{|\nu|})}^* \end{aligned}$$

if $a = \nu_1$. So

$$\psi \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) S_{\xi_a} = S_{\xi_a} \psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(\mathbf{1}_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(C(\mu))} \right) \right)$$

and hence

$$S_{\xi_a}^* \psi \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) = \psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) \right) S_{\xi_a}^*.$$

So since $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, we have that

$$\psi(f) S_{\xi_a} = S_{\xi_a} \psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f))$$

for all $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, and hence

$$\psi(f) \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} = \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} \psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)) = \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} \psi'(\phi(f))$$

for all $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ and all $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$.

For every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}^* \tilde{T}_{(g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) S_a^* \sum_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{a'} \psi(g_{a'}) \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) S_a^* S_a \psi(g_a) \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) \psi(1_{\sigma(C(a))}) \psi(g_a) \\ &= \psi \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} f_a^* g_a \right) \\ &= \psi(\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \rangle). \end{aligned}$$

Finally we see that for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ is $\phi'(f) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f) \otimes \xi_a^*$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{(1)}(\phi'(f)) &= \psi^{(1)} \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f) \otimes \xi_a^* \right) \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_{\xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f)} \tilde{T}_{\xi_a}^* \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)) S_a^* \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f) S_a S_a^* \\ &= \psi(f). \end{aligned}$$

So by Proposition 2.1.6 there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ sending $S_a = S_{\xi_a}$ to $\tilde{T}_{\xi_a} = S_a$.

Since $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ are generated by S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ the two $*$ -homomorphisms are each other inverse, and hence $\tilde{\rho}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ that sends S_a to S_a for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. $\square$

We will for the sake of convenience from now on denote $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}_\Lambda}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ by $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$.

Notes

All the material covered in Section 2.1 is taken from [22]. I have chosen to emphasize the maps ι and $\iota^{(n)}$ that are implied in [22].

Section 2.4 is an elucidation of some of the material considered in [11] and essentially goes back [4] and [6]. Lemma 2.4.1 is an exercise (Exercise 2.4) in [25], Lemma 2.4.3 is Lemma 3.1 and Corollary 3.4 of [11] and Proposition 2.4.6 is Lemma 4.6 of [11].

Chapter 3

Properties of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$

In this chapter we will discuss some of the properties of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$. We will prove that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is a generalization of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras and we will discuss its relation with the C^* -algebras Matsumoto has associated to a two-sided shift space.

3.1 The universal property of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$

Theorem 2.1.6 tells us that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ has a universal property. But we want to reformulated this universal property in a way that is reminiscent of the universal property of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras.

Theorem 3.1.1. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. If $\mathcal{X}$ is a C^* -algebra such that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism ψ from $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ and there are partial isometries $\tilde{T}_a$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ satisfying the following relations:*

- a) $\sum_{i \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_i \tilde{T}_i^* = \psi(I)$,
- b) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* = \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu$,
- c) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu = \psi(S_\mu^* S_\mu)$,

where $\tilde{T}_\mu = \tilde{T}_{\mu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $\tilde{T}_\nu = \tilde{T}_{\nu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$ for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, then there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(S_a) = \tilde{T}_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.

Proof. Set

$$\tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \psi(f_a)$$

for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.

Then $\alpha \tilde{T}_\xi + \beta \tilde{T}_\zeta = \tilde{T}_{\alpha \xi + \beta \zeta}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$, and $\tilde{T}_\xi \psi(f) = \tilde{T}_{\xi f}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$.

We also have that

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} &= \psi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \psi(f_a) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_a \psi(f_a) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \tilde{T}_{\mu a}^* \tilde{T}_{\mu a} \psi(f_a) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \psi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu a|} (C(\mu a)) \right) \psi(f_a) \\
&= \tilde{T}_{\left(1_{\sigma|\mu a|} (C(\mu a)) f_a \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} \\
&= \tilde{T}_{\left(\tilde{\lambda}_a \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) f_a \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} \\
&= \tilde{T}_{\phi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}},
\end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$\tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}^* \psi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) = \tilde{T}_{\phi \left(1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu)) \right) (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}^*$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$. Since $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{\sigma|\mu|} (C(\mu))$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, we have that

$$\psi(f) \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} = \tilde{T}_{\phi(f) (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}$$

for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ and every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.

Since

$$\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \tilde{T}_a^* = \psi(1) \leq I,$$

it follows from Lemma 2.4.1 that

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{T}_a^* \tilde{T}_{a'} &= \tilde{T}_a^* \tilde{T}_a \tilde{T}_a^* \tilde{T}_{a'} \tilde{T}_a^* \tilde{T}_{a'} \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

if $a \neq a'$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}^* \tilde{T}_{(g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}} &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) \tilde{T}_a^* \sum_{a' \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_{a'} \psi(g_{a'}) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) \tilde{T}_a^* \tilde{T}_a \psi(g_a) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f_a^*) \psi \left(1_{\sigma(C(a))} \right) \psi(g_a) \\
&= \psi(\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \rangle)
\end{aligned}$$

for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.

Finally we see that for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is $\phi(f) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f) \otimes \xi_a^*$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{(1)}(\phi(f)) &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} T_{\xi_a \tilde{\lambda}_a(f)} T_{\xi_a}^* \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)) \tilde{T}_a^* \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \psi(f) \tilde{T}_a \tilde{T}_a^* \\ &= \psi(f). \end{aligned}$$

So it follows from Theorem 2.1.6 that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(S_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}) = \tilde{T}_{(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}}$ for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and hence

$$\tilde{\psi}(S_a) = \tilde{\psi}(S_{\xi_a}) = \tilde{T}_{\xi_a} = \tilde{T}_a$$

for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. □

3.2 Generalizations of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras

We are now able to show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ in fact is a generalization of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras. Actual we will prove that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is a generalization of the universal Cuntz-Krieger algebra $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{O}_A$ that An Huef and Raeburn have constructed in [1].

Theorem 3.2.1. *Let A be a $n \times n$ -matrix with entries in $\{0, 1\}$. Then $\mathcal{O}_{\Lambda_A}$ is generated by partial isometries S_i , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ that satisfy*

$$\sum_{j=1}^n S_j S_j^* = I,$$

and

$$S_i^* S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n A(i, j) S_j S_j^*$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

If $\mathcal{X}$ is a unital C^* -algebra such that there exist partial isometries $\tilde{T}_i$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ that satisfy

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^* = I,$$

and

$$\tilde{T}_i^* \tilde{T}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n A(i, j) \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^*$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$; then there exists a $*$ -homomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_{\Lambda_A}$ to $\mathcal{X}$ sending S_i to $\tilde{T}_i$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Proof. We have already seen that

$$\sum_{j=1}^n S_j S_j^* = I.$$

It is easy to check that

$$\sigma(C(i)) = \bigcup_{A(i, j)=1} C(j),$$

and hence

$$1_{\sigma(C(i))} = \sum_{j=1}^n A(i, j) 1_{C(j)}$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$; and it thus follows from Lemma 2.3.4 that

$$S_i^* S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n A(i, j) S_j S_j^*$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Now let $\mathcal{X}$ be a unital C^* -algebra such that there exist partial isometries $\tilde{T}_i$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ that satisfy

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^* = I,$$

and

$$\tilde{T}_i^* \tilde{T}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n A(i, j) \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^*$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. It follows from Lemma 2.4.1 that $\tilde{T}_i \tilde{T}_i^*$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ are orthogonal projections, and since $1_{C(i)}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ also are orthogonal projections, there exists a unital $*$ -homomorphism ψ from the C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{D}_{\Lambda_A}$ generated by $1_{C(i)}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\psi(1_{C(i)}) = \tilde{T}_i \tilde{T}_i^*$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

It is easy to check that

$$1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))} = \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n A(\mu_{|\mu|}, j) 1_{C(j)} & \text{if } \mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A) \\ 0 & \text{if } \mu \notin \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A), \end{cases}$$

and that

$$\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu = \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n A(\mu_{|\mu|}, j) \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^* & \text{if } \mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A) \\ 0 & \text{if } \mu \notin \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A). \end{cases}$$

So $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda_A}$ is a C^* -subalgebra of the C^* -subalgebra of $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda_A}$ generated by $1_{C(i)}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\psi(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}) = \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu$ for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\{1, 2, \dots, n\}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Furthermore

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* &= \sum_{j=1}^n A(\mu_{|\mu|}, j) \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^* \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \\ &= A(\mu_{|\mu|}, \nu_1) \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \\ &= \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \sum_{j=1}^n A(\mu_{|\mu|}, j) \tilde{T}_j \tilde{T}_j^* \\ &= \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \end{aligned}$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A)$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\{1, 2, \dots, n\}^{\mathbb{N}})$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* &= 0 \\ &= \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \end{aligned}$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\{1, 2, \dots, n\}^{\mathbb{N}}) \setminus \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_A)$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\{1, 2, \dots, n\}^{\mathbb{N}})$.

Hence it follows from Theorem 3.1.1 that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_{\Lambda_A}$ to $\mathcal{X}$ sending S_i to $\tilde{T}_i$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. $\square$

3.3 Uniqueness of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$

One of the most interesting things about Cuntz-Krieger algebras is that if the matrix A satisfies a certain condition (I), then all C^* -algebras that are generated by non-zero partial isometries that satisfy the Cuntz-Krieger relations for A are canonically isomorphic.

We will now prove a similar result for $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$.

Proposition 3.3.1. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Define a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda : \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda) \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ by letting*

$$\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(f)(x) = f(\sigma(x))$$

for every $f \in \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ and every $x \in \Lambda$.

Then $\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.

Proof. Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. Then

$$\sigma^{-1}(C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))) = \bigcup_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} C(a\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))),$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\phi}_\Lambda \left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \right) &= 1_{\sigma^{-1}(C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))))} \\ &= 1_{\bigcup_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} C(a\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} 1_{C(a\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

So since $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ and $\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda$ is a *-homomorphism it follows that $\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$. $\square$

For every one-sided shift space we will denote $\iota(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda)$ by $\mathcal{D}_\Lambda$.

Lemma 3.3.2. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then*

$$\iota(\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(f)) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \iota(f) S_a^*,$$

and

$$\iota(\tilde{\lambda}_{a'}(f)) = S_{a'}^* \iota(f) S_{a'}$$

for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ and every $a' \in \mathfrak{A}$.

Proof. Let for every $X \in \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$ and every $a' \in \mathfrak{A}$

$$\phi_\Lambda(X) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a X S_a^*$$

and

$$\lambda_{a'}(X) = S_{a'}^* X S_{a'}.$$

It is easy to check that $\phi_\Lambda : \mathcal{D}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ and $\lambda_{a'} : \mathcal{D}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda}$ are linear maps, and that $\phi_\Lambda(X)^* = \phi_\Lambda(X^*)$ and $\lambda_{a'}(X)^* = \lambda_{a'}(X^*)$ for every $X \in \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$.

Let $X, Y \in \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi_\Lambda(X)\phi_\Lambda(Y) &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a X S_a^* \sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}} S_b Y S_b^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a X S_a^* S_a Y S_a^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a X \iota(1_{\sigma(C(a))}) Y S_a^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \iota(1_{\sigma(C(a))}) X Y S_a^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* S_a X Y S_a^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a X Y S_a^* \\
&= \phi_\Lambda(XY),
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda_{a'}(X)\lambda_{a'}(Y) &= S_{a'}^* X S_{a'} S_{a'}^* Y S_{a'} \\
&= S_{a'}^* X \iota(1_{C(a')}) Y S_{a'} \\
&= S_{a'}^* \iota(1_{C(a')}) X Y S_{a'} \\
&= S_{a'}^* S_{a'} S_{a'}^* X Y S_{a'} \\
&= S_{a'}^* X Y S_{a'} \\
&= \lambda_{a'}(XY).
\end{aligned}$$

So ϕ_Λ and $\lambda_{a'}$ are *-homomorphisms.

Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\iota\left(\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda\left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right) &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \iota\left(1_{C(a\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu a|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{a\nu} S_\mu^* S_\mu S_{a\nu}^* \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \iota\left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right) S_a^* \\
&= \phi_\Lambda\left(\iota\left(1_{C(\nu) \cap \sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right),
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\iota\left(\tilde{\lambda}_{a'}\left(1_{C^{(\nu)}\cap\sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right) &= \begin{cases} \iota\left(1_{C^{((\nu_2,\dots,\nu_{|\nu|})\cap\sigma^{1-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))))}1_{\sigma(C(a))}\right) & \text{if } a' = \nu_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } a' \neq \nu_1 \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} S_{(\nu_2,\dots,\nu_{|\nu|})}S_\mu^*S_\mu S_{(\nu_2,\dots,\nu_{|\nu|})}^*S_{\nu_1}^*S_{\nu_1} & \text{if } a' = \nu_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } a' \neq \nu_1 \end{cases} \\
&= S_{a'}^*S_\nu S_\mu^*S_\mu S_\nu^*S_{a'}^* \\
&= \lambda_{a'}\left(\iota\left(1_{C^{(\nu)}\cap\sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right),
\end{aligned}$$

if $|\nu| \geq 1$, and if $\nu = \emptyset$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\iota\left(\tilde{\lambda}_{a'}\left(1_{C^{(\nu)}\cap\sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right) &= \iota\left(\tilde{\lambda}_{a'}\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}\right)\right) \\
&= \iota\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu a'|}(C(\mu a'))}\right) \\
&= S_{\mu a'}^*S_{\mu a'} \\
&= S_{a'}^*S_\mu^*S_\mu S_{a'} \\
&= \lambda_{a'}\left(\iota\left(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}\right)\right) \\
&= \lambda_{a'}\left(\iota\left(1_{C^{(\nu)}\cap\sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}\right)\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{C^{(\nu)}\cap\sigma^{-|\nu|}(\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)))}$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ it follows that

$$\iota(\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(f)) = \phi_\Lambda(\iota(f)) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a \iota(f) S_a^*$$

and

$$\iota(\tilde{\lambda}_{a'}(f)) = \lambda_{a'}(\iota(f)) = S_{a'}^* \iota(f) S_{a'}$$

for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ and every $a' \in \mathfrak{A}$. $\square$

Definition 3.3.3. For a one-sided shift space Λ we let $\phi_\Lambda : \mathcal{D}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$ be the $*$ -homomorphism $\iota \circ \tilde{\phi}_\Lambda \circ \iota^{-1}$, and we let for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, $\lambda_a : \mathcal{D}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$ be the $*$ -homomorphism $\iota \circ \tilde{\lambda}_a \circ \iota^{-1}$.

Lemma 3.3.4. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then we have:

- If $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2$ are subsets of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}_1}, 1_{\mathcal{E}_2} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, then $1_{\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.
- If $\mathcal{E}$ is a subset of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, then $1_{\sigma(\mathcal{E})} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.
- If $\mathcal{E}$ is a subset of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, then $1_{\sigma^{-1}(\mathcal{E})} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.

Proof. a) Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2$ be subsets of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}_1}, 1_{\mathcal{E}_2} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$, then

$$1_{\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2} = 1_{\mathcal{E}_1} + 1_{\mathcal{E}_2} - 1_{\mathcal{E}_1} 1_{\mathcal{E}_2} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda.$$

b) Let $\mathcal{E}$ be a subset of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$. Set for each $a \in \mathfrak{A}$,

$$\mathcal{F}_a = \{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}\}.$$

It is easy to check that

$$\sigma(\mathcal{E}) = \bigcup_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \mathcal{F}_a.$$

Since $1_{\mathcal{F}_a} = \tilde{\lambda}_a(1_{\mathcal{E}}) \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ (cf. Proposition 2.2.3), it follows from a) that $1_{\sigma(\mathcal{E})} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$.

c) Let $\mathcal{E}$ be a subset of Λ such that $1_{\mathcal{E}} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$. It is easy to check that $1_{\sigma^{-1}(\mathcal{E})} = \tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(1_{\mathcal{E}})$, so $1_{\sigma^{-1}(\mathcal{E})} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Lambda$ by Lemma 3.3.1. $\square$

We are now ready to describe the condition (I) for a one-sided shift space Λ . For each $x \in \Lambda$ and each $l \in \mathbb{N}$ we let

$$\Lambda^l(x) = \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda) \mid \mu x \in \Lambda\}.$$

Two points $x, y \in \Lambda$ are said to be l -past equivalent if $\Lambda^l(x) = \Lambda^l(y)$. It is easy to see that this is an equivalence relation. We write this equivalence as $x \sim_l y$. Let $\mathcal{E}_i^l$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ be the l -past equivalence classes of Λ .

For a subset $\mathcal{E}$ of Λ and $l \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $\Lambda^l(\mathcal{E})$ the set $\{\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda) \mid \forall x \in \mathcal{E} : \mu x \in \Lambda\}$ and by $\Lambda_l(\mathcal{E})$ the set $\{\mu \in \mathcal{B}_l(\Lambda) \mid \forall x \in \mathcal{E} : \mu x \in \Lambda\}$.

Proposition 3.3.5. *Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then*

$$\iota \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$$

are mutually orthogonal projections such that

$$\left(\iota \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} \right) \right)_{1,2,\dots,m(l)}$$

is a basis for $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$.

Proof. Since $\mathcal{E}_i^l$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ are mutually orthogonal disjoint sets,

$$\iota \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$$

are mutually orthogonal projections.

Since

$$\mathcal{E}_i^l = \left(\bigcap_{\mu \in \Lambda^l(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} \sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)) \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{\nu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda) \setminus \Lambda^l(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} \Lambda \setminus \sigma^{|\nu|}(C(\mu)) \right)$$

for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, we have that

$$\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) = \left(\prod_{\mu \in \Lambda^l(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} S_\mu^* S_\mu \right) \left(\prod_{\nu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda) \setminus \Lambda^l(\mathcal{E}_i^l)} (I - S_\nu^* S_\nu) \right)$$

and hence $\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) \in \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$.

For each $\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(\Lambda)$ let $\Lambda^l(\mu) = \{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\} \mid \mu \in \Lambda^l(\mathcal{E}_i^l)\}$. Then

$$\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)) = \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda^l(\mu)} \mathcal{E}_i^l.$$

So

$$S_\mu^* S_\mu = \iota(1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu))}) = \sum_{i \in \Lambda^l(\mu)} \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}).$$

Hence $\text{span}\{\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) \mid i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}\} = \mathcal{A}_l$. So

$$(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})_{1,2,\dots,m(l)}$$

is a basis for $\mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. $\square$

Proposition 3.3.6. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then the following are equivalent:*

- For any $l \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x \in \Lambda$, there exists $y \in \Lambda$ such that $x \neq y$ and $x \sim_l y$.
- For any $l, m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x \in \Lambda$, there exists $y \in \Lambda$ such that $y_j = x_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, m$, $y_N \neq x_N$ for some $N > m$ and $y \sim_l x$.
- For any pair $l, m \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $y^i \in \mathcal{E}_i^l$ for $i = 1, \dots, m(l)$ such that $\sigma^k(y^i) \neq y^j$ for all $i, j = 1, \dots, m(l)$ and $k = 1, \dots, m$.
- For any $l \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a projection Q^l in $\mathcal{D}_\Lambda$ such that $Q^l A \neq 0$ for any nonzero $A \in \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$, and $Q^l \phi_\Lambda^m(Q^l) = 0$ for $1 \leq m \leq l$.

Proof. a) $\Rightarrow$ b): Given $l, m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x \in \Lambda$. Put $\mu = (x_1, \dots, x_m)$ and $x' = (x_{m+1}, x_{m+2}, \dots)$. Then there exists $w \in \Lambda$ such that $x' \neq w$ and $x' \sim_{m+l} w$. If we let $y = \mu w$, then $y \in \Lambda$, $y_j = x_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, m$, $y_N \neq x_N$ for some $N > m$ and $y \sim_l x$.

b) $\Rightarrow$ c): Given $l, m \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $\prec$ be the lexicographic ordering on

$$K = \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \times \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\} \times \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}.$$

For each $(k_0, i_0, j_0) \in K$ let $H(k_0, i_0, j_0)$ be the set

$$\{(y^1, \dots, y^{m(l)}) \in \mathcal{E}_1^l \times \dots \times \mathcal{E}_{m(l)}^l \mid \forall (k, i, j) \preceq (k_0, i_0, j_0) : \sigma^k(y^i) \neq y^j\}.$$

We want to show that $H(m, m(l), m(l)) \neq \emptyset$. So assume that $H(m, m(l), m(l)) = \emptyset$. Let (k_0, i_0, j_0) be the first element in $(K, \preceq)$ such that $H(k_0, i_0, j_0) = \emptyset$. Since we assume b), $H(1, 1, 1) \neq \emptyset$, so there exists an element before (k_0, i_0, j_0) . Let (k_1, i_1, j_1) be the last element before (k_0, i_0, j_0) and choose

$$(y^1, \dots, y^{m(l)}) \in H(k_1, i_1, j_1).$$

Then $\sigma^{k_0}(y^{i_0}) = y^{j_0}$, since $H(m, m(l), m(l)) = \emptyset$. Choose for each $(k, i, j) \preceq (k_1, i_1, j_1)$ a $n(k, i, j) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $(\sigma^k(y^i))_{n(k, i, j)} \neq y_{n(k, i, j)}^j$. Let

$$M = \max\{n(k, i, j) \mid (k, i, j) \preceq (k_1, i_1, j_1)\}.$$

Since we assume b) is true, there exists a $y \in \mathcal{E}_{i_0}^l$ such that $y_N \neq y_N^{i_0}$ for some $N > k_0 + M$ and $y_h = y_h^{i_0}$ for $h = 1, 2, \dots, M + k_0$. Hence

$$(y^1, y^2, \dots, y^{i_0-1}, y, y^{i_0+1}, \dots, y^{m(l)}) \in H(k_0, i_0, j_0).$$

Contradiction! So $H(m, m(l), m(l)) \neq \emptyset$ and c) is true.

c) $\Rightarrow$ d): Given $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Choose $y^i \in \mathcal{E}_i^l$ for $i = 1, \dots, m(l)$ such that $\sigma^m(y^i) \neq y^j$ for all $i, j = 1, \dots, m(l)$ and $m = 1, \dots, l$. Set

$$Y = \{y^i \mid i = 1, \dots, m(l)\}.$$

Then $\sigma^m(Y) \cap Y = \emptyset$ for $1 \leq m \leq l$. Since Λ is Hausdorff, Y is closed and hence compact, and since σ is continuous, $\sigma^m(Y)$ is compact and closed for all $1 \leq m \leq l$. So since Λ is normal there exist open sets U_m , $0 \leq m \leq l$ such that $\sigma^m(Y) \subseteq U_m$ for all $0 \leq m \leq l$, and $U_0 \cap U_m = \emptyset$ for all $1 \leq m \leq l$.

Since $C(\mu)$, $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ is a basis for the topology of Λ , and $\sigma^m(Y)$ is closed and hence compact for each $0 \leq m \leq l$ there exist a finite number r_m of words $\mu_1^m, \mu_2^m, \dots, \mu_{r_m}^m \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ such that

$$\sigma^m(Y) \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} C(\mu_i^m) \subseteq U_m$$

for all $0 \leq m \leq l$. Set

$$\mathcal{E} = \bigcap_{m=0}^l \bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} \sigma^{-m}(C(\mu_i^m)),$$

and

$$Q^l = \iota(1\mathcal{E}).$$

Then it follows from Lemma 3.3.4 that $Q^l \in \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$. Since $\sigma^m(Y) \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} C(\mu_i^m)$, and hence $Y \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} \sigma^{-m}(C(\mu_i^m))$ for all $0 \leq m \leq l$, we have

that $Y \subseteq \mathcal{E}$. For all $0 \leq m \leq l$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^m(\mathcal{E}) &\subseteq \sigma^m \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} \sigma^{-m}(C(\mu_i^m)) \right) \\ &\subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^{r_m} C(\mu_i^m) \\ &\subseteq U_m, \end{aligned}$$

so since $U_0 \cap U_m$ for all $1 \leq m \leq l$,

$$\mathcal{E} \cap \sigma^m(\mathcal{E}) = \emptyset$$

and hence

$$\mathcal{E} \cap \sigma^{-m}(\mathcal{E}) = \emptyset$$

for all $1 \leq m \leq l$.

If $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$ is nonzero then there exists $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_i^l \subseteq \text{supp}(f)$ and hence $f(y^i) \neq 0$. Since $y^i \in Y \subseteq \mathcal{E}$, we have that $Q^l \iota(f) \neq 0$. So $Q^l A \neq 0$ for any nonzero $A \in \mathcal{A}_l$.

Finally we see that

$$1_{\mathcal{E}} \tilde{\phi}_\Lambda^m(1_{\mathcal{E}}) = 1_{\mathcal{E} \cap \sigma^{-m}(\mathcal{E})} = 0$$

for every $1 \leq m \leq l$, so $Q^l \phi_\Lambda^m(Q^l) = 0$ for $1 \leq m \leq l$.

d) $\Rightarrow$ c): Given $l, m \in \mathbb{N}$. For each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m(l)$ pick an element y^i in the support of $\iota^{-1}(Q^l)1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}$. Then $\sigma^k(y^i) \neq y^j$ for all $i, j = 1, \dots, m(l)$ and $k = 1, \dots, m$.

c) $\Rightarrow$ a): Suppose that there exist an $l \in \mathbb{N}$ and an $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_i^l$ is one point y . Let $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ be such that $y \in \mathcal{E}_j^{l+1}$. Then $\mathcal{E}_j^{l+1} = \{y\}$. By c) we have that $\sigma(y) \neq y$. So $\sigma(y) \in \mathcal{E}_k^{l+1}$ for some $k \neq j$. For any $z \in \mathcal{E}_k^{l+1}$ we have that $y \sim_l y_1 \sigma(y) \sim_l y_1 z$, hence $y_1 z = y$. So $\mathcal{E}_k^{l+1} = \{\sigma(y)\}$. But since $\mathcal{E}_j^{l+1} = \{y\}$ and $k \neq j$ this contradicts c).

b) $\Rightarrow$ a): Trivial. $\square$

Definition 3.3.7. Let Λ be a one-sided shift space such that the conditions in Proposition 3.3.6 are satisfied. Then we say that Λ satisfies condition (I).

One can show that if A is a $n \times n$ -matrix with entries in $\{0, 1\}$, then the one-sided shift space Λ_A defined in Example 1.0.5 satisfies condition (I) if and only if the matrix A satisfies the condition (I) considered in [6].

Now assume that Λ is a one-sided shift space that satisfies condition (I). For every $1 \leq k \leq l$ we denote $\phi_\Lambda^k(Q^l)$ by Q_k^l . Then we have the following lemmas:

Lemma 3.3.8. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. For $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda)$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}_l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ is $S_\mu AS_\nu^* = 0$ if and only if $Q_k^l S_\mu AS_\nu^* = 0$.*

Proof. It follows from Lemma 3.3.2 that

$$\begin{aligned} Q_k^l S_\mu AS_\nu^* &= \phi_\Lambda^k(Q^l) S_\mu AS_\nu^* \\ &= \sum_{\alpha \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})} S_\alpha Q^l S_\alpha^* S_\mu AS_\nu^* \\ &= S_\mu Q^l A_\mu AS_\nu^*, \end{aligned}$$

so if $Q_k^l S_\mu AS_\nu^* = 0$ then $Q^l A_\mu A_\nu A = S_\mu^* S_\mu Q^l A_\mu AS_\nu^* S_\nu = 0$, and hence $A_\mu A_\nu A = 0$. Thus $S_\mu AS_\nu^* = S_\mu A_\mu A A_\nu S_\nu = 0$. $\square$

Lemma 3.3.9. *Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Each element of $\phi_\Lambda^k(\mathcal{D}_\Lambda)$ commutes with any element of $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$.*

Proof. Let $X \in \mathcal{D}_\Lambda$, $\nu, \nu' \in \mathcal{B}_k(\Lambda)$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}_\Lambda(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_\Lambda^k(X) S_\nu AS_{\nu'}^* &= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})} S_\mu X S_\mu^* S_\nu AS_{\nu'}^* \\ &= S_\nu X A_\nu AS_{\nu'}^* \\ &= S_\nu X A_\nu A A_{\nu'} S_{\nu'}^* \\ &= S_\nu A_\nu A A_{\nu'} X S_{\nu'}^* \\ &= S_\nu A A_{\nu'} X S_{\nu'}^* \\ &= S_\nu AS_{\nu'}^* \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})} S_\mu X S_\mu^* \\ &= S_\nu AS_{\nu'}^* \phi_\Lambda^k(X). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ is generated by $S_\nu AS_{\nu'}^*$, $\nu, \nu' \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$, $A \in \mathcal{A}_\Lambda(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ it follows that each element of $\phi_\Lambda^k(\mathcal{D}_\Lambda)$ commutes with any element of $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. $\square$

The following lemma easily follows from Lemma 2.4.5, 3.3.8 and 3.3.9.

Lemma 3.3.10. *For every $1 \leq k \leq l$ there exists a $*$ -isomorphism $\psi_k^l : \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \rightarrow Q_k^l \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) Q_k^l$ such that $\psi_k^l(X) = Q_k^l X Q_k^l$ for all $X \in \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$.*

Lemma 3.3.11. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. For every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$ with $1 \leq |\mu| \leq l$ is $Q_k^l S_\mu Q_k^l = 0$.*

Proof. Let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$, $1 \leq |\mu| \leq l$. Then it follows from Lemma 3.3.2,

Lemma 3.3.9 and the fact that $Q^l \phi_\Lambda^m(Q^l) = 0$ for $1 \leq m \leq l$ that

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_k^l S_\mu Q_k^l &= Q_k^l S_\mu S_\mu^* S_\mu Q_k^l \\
&= Q_k^l S_\mu Q_k^l S_\mu^* S_\mu \\
&= Q_k^l \phi_\Lambda^{|\mu|}(Q_k^l) S_\mu \\
&= \phi_\Lambda^k(Q^l \phi_\Lambda^{|\mu|}(Q^l)) S_\mu \\
&= 0.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.3.12. *For each $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and each $\epsilon > 0$ there exist $1 \leq k \leq l$ such that*

$$\|X\| \leq \|Q_{k+n}^{l+n+m} X Q_{k+n}^{l+n+m}\| + \epsilon$$

for every $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

Proof. Let $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and $\epsilon > 0$. Since $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) = \overline{\bigcup_{1 \leq k \leq l} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)}$ there exist $1 \leq k \leq l$ and $X_0 \in \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ such that $\|X - X_0\| < \epsilon/2$. Since $X_0 \in \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \subseteq \mathcal{F}_{k+n}^{l+n+m}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ for every $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_0$, it follows from Lemma 3.3.10 that

$$\begin{aligned}
\|X\| &\leq \|X_0\| + \epsilon/2 \\
&= \|Q_{k+n}^{l+n+m} X_0 Q_{k+n}^{l+n+m}\| + \epsilon/2 \\
&\leq \|Q_{k+n}^{l+n+m} X Q_{k+n}^{k+n+m}\| + \epsilon
\end{aligned}$$

for every $n, m \in \mathbb{N}_0$. □

Lemma 3.3.13. *For every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$, every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$ with $|\mu| \geq 1$ and every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists a $K \in \mathbb{N}$ such that*

$$\|Q_k^l S_\mu X Q_k^l\| < \epsilon$$

for every $K \leq k \leq l$.

Proof. Since $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) = \overline{\bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)}$ there exist a $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and a $X_0 \in \mathcal{F}_n^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ such that $\|X - X_0\| < \epsilon$. Set $K = \max\{n, |\mu|\}$. Since $X_0 \in \mathcal{F}_n^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \subseteq \mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ for every $k \geq K$, it follows from Lemma 3.3.9 and Lemma 3.3.11 that

$$\begin{aligned}
\|Q_k^l S_\mu X Q_k^l\| &\leq \epsilon + \|Q_k^l S_\mu X_0 Q_k^l\| \\
&\leq \epsilon + \|Q_k^l\| \|S_\mu\| \|X_0 Q_k^l - Q_k^l X_0\| + \|Q_k^l S_\mu Q_k^l\| \|X_0\| \\
&= \epsilon
\end{aligned}$$

for every $K \leq k \leq l$. □

Proposition 3.3.14. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space that satisfies condition (I). If $\mathcal{O}$ is a unital C^* -algebra generated by partial isometries $\tilde{T}_a$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, and there exists an injective, unital $*$ -homomorphism ψ from $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{O}$ such that*

- a) $\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_a \tilde{T}_a^* = I$,
- b) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* = \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu$,
- c) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu = \psi(S_\mu^* S_\mu)$,

where $\tilde{T}_\mu = \tilde{T}_{\mu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $\tilde{T}_\nu = \tilde{T}_{\nu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, then there exists a continuous, linear map

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{O}} : \mathcal{O} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$$

such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = X$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\tilde{T}_\nu X) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X \tilde{T}_\nu^*) = 0$ for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$.

Proof. From Theorem 3.1.1 we know that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{O}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(S_a) = \tilde{T}_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.

From Lemma 2.4.3 we know that every element $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$ can be written as a finite sum

$$X = \sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X_{-\nu} \tilde{T}_\nu^* + X_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} \tilde{T}_\mu X_\mu$$

for some $X_{-\nu}, X_0, X_\mu \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$. We want to show that X_0 is uniquely determined by X and that $\|X_0\| \leq \|X\|$.

Given $\epsilon > 0$. Since $\tilde{\psi}|_{\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)}$ is an $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O})$ we know from Proposition 2.4.6 that $\tilde{\psi}|_{\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)}$ is an $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$. So it follows from Lemma 3.3.12 and Lemma 3.3.13 that there exist $1 \leq k \leq l$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l) X Q_l^k\| &\geq \|\tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l) X_0 \tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l)\| - \left(\sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} \|\tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l) X_{-\nu} \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l)\| \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} \|\tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l) \tilde{T}_\mu X_\mu \tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l)\| \right) \geq \|X_0\| - \epsilon \end{aligned}$$

Since $\|\tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l) X \tilde{\psi}(Q_k^l)\| \leq \|X\|$ for every $1 \leq k \leq l$, it follows that $\|X_0\| \leq \|X\|$. If we could write

$$X = \sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X'_{-\nu} \tilde{T}_\nu^* + X'_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} \tilde{T}_\mu X'_\mu$$

for some different $X'_{-\nu}, X'_0, X'_\mu \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$, then

$$0 = \sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} (X_{-\nu} - X'_{-\nu}) \tilde{T}_\nu^* + (X_0 - X'_0) + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} \tilde{T}_\mu (X_\mu - X'_\mu)$$

and $\|X_0 - X'_0\| \leq \|0\| = 0$ and hence $X_0 = X'_0$.

We can therefore define a continuous, linear map $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}} : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O}) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ by setting $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = X_0$ for every $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O})$, and by continuity extend it to a continuous, linear map from $\mathcal{O}$ to $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = X$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\tilde{T}_\nu X) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X \tilde{T}_\nu^*) = 0$ for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$. $\square$

Theorem 3.3.15. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space that satisfies condition (I). If $\mathcal{X}$ is a C^* -algebra such that there exists an injective $*$ -homomorphism ψ from $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ and there are partial isometries $\tilde{T}_a$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ satisfying the following relations:*

- a) $\sum_{i \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_i \tilde{T}_i^* = \psi(I)$,
- b) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* = \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu$,
- c) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu = \psi(S_\mu^* S_\mu)$,

where $\tilde{T}_\mu = \tilde{T}_{\mu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $\tilde{T}_\nu = \tilde{T}_{\nu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$ for all $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$, then there exists an injective $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(S_a) = \tilde{T}_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.

Proof. From Theorem 3.1.1 we know that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\tilde{\psi}(S_a) = \tilde{T}_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. So we just have to show that $\tilde{\psi}$ is injective.

By Remark 2.1.1 and Proposition 2.4.7 there exists a faithful, continuous, linear map $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda} : \mathcal{O}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(X) = X$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(S_\nu X) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(X S_\nu^*) = 0$ for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$.

Let $\mathcal{O}$ be the C^* -algebra of $\mathcal{X}$ generated by $\tilde{T}_a$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. Then $\psi(I)$ is a unit for $\mathcal{O}$, so it follows from Proposition 3.3.14 that there exists a continuous, linear map

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{O}} : \mathcal{O} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$$

such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X) = X$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\tilde{T}_\nu X) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(X \tilde{T}_\nu^*) = 0$ for every $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O})$ and every $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ with $|\nu| \geq 1$.

Since

$$\tilde{\psi} \left(\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda} \left(\sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X_{-\nu} S_\nu^* + X_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} S_\mu X_\mu \right) \right) = \tilde{\psi}(X_0),$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\mathcal{O}} \left(\tilde{\psi} \left(\sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} X_{-\nu} S_\nu^* + X_0 + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} S_\mu X_\mu \right) \right) &= \\ \Phi_{\mathcal{O}} \left(\sum_{|\nu| \geq 1} \tilde{\psi}(X_{-\nu}) \tilde{T}_\nu^* + \tilde{\psi}(X_0) + \sum_{|\mu| \geq 1} \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{\psi}(X_\mu) \right) &= \tilde{\psi}(X_0) \end{aligned}$$

for $X_{-\nu}, X_\mu, X_0 \in \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}^\infty$, we have that $\tilde{\psi} \circ \Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(Y) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}} \circ \tilde{\psi}(Y)$ for every $Y \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$, and since $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ is dense in $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ and $\tilde{\psi}$, $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}}$ are continuous it follows that $\tilde{\psi} \circ \Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda} = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}} \circ \tilde{\psi}$. By Proposition 2.4.6 we know that $\tilde{\psi}|_{\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)}$ is a *-isomorphism, so if $\tilde{\psi}(X) = 0$, then

$$\tilde{\psi}(\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(X^*X)) = \Phi_{\mathcal{O}}(\tilde{\psi}(X^*X)) = 0,$$

and hence $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(X^*X) = 0$, and since $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}$ is faithful we have that $X^*X = 0$, and thus $X = 0$. So $\tilde{\psi}$ is injective $\square$

3.4 C^* -algebras associated with two-sided shift spaces

Let X be a two-sided shift space as defined in [10]. Then the language $\mathcal{B}(X)$ of X satisfies the following: If $w \in \mathcal{B}(X)$, then

- a) every subword of w belongs to $\mathcal{B}(X)$, and
- b) there are nonempty words u and v in $\mathcal{L}$ so that $uvw \in \mathcal{L}$.

(cf. Proposition 1.3.4 in [10].)

Thus it follows from Proposition 1.0.6 that there exists a unique one-sided shift space Λ such that $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \mathcal{B}(X)$. We denote Λ by X^+ . It is easy to show that X^+ is the set of all right infinite sequences that appear in elements of X . In this way one can think of one-sided shift spaces as a generalization of two-sided shift spaces. We of course have that a one-sided shift space Λ is equal to X^+ for some two-sided shift space X , if and only if there for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ exists a nonempty word $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ such that $\nu\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. One can show that this is equivalent to $\sigma(\Lambda) = \Lambda$. Not every one-sided shift space satisfies this condition. For instance $\Lambda = X_{\{11,21\}}$ does not.

Matsumoto has in [11] to every two-sided shift space X associated a unital C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_X$ generated by partial isometries S_a , $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ that satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_a S_a^* &= I, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu S_\nu^* &= S_\nu S_\nu^* S_\mu^* S_\mu, \\ S_\mu^* S_\mu S_\nu^* S_\nu &= S_\nu^* S_\nu S_\mu^* S_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

where $S_\mu = S_{\mu_1} \cdots S_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $S_\nu = S_{\nu_1} \cdots S_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$, for every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$; and has claimed that $\mathcal{O}_X$ is characterized by the following Theorem and Lemma:

Theorem 3.4.1 (Theorem 4.9 of [11]). *Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a unital C^* -algebra. Suppose that there is a unital $*$ -homomorphism π from $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O}_X)$ to $\mathcal{X}$ and there are partial isometries $\tilde{T}_a$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ satisfying the following relations:*

- a) $\sum_{i \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{T}_i \tilde{T}_i^* = I$,
- b) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* = \tilde{T}_\nu \tilde{T}_\nu^* \tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu$,
- c) $\tilde{T}_\mu^* \tilde{T}_\mu = \pi(S_\mu^* S_\mu)$,

where $\tilde{T}_\mu = \tilde{T}_{\mu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\mu_{|\mu|}}$ and $\tilde{T}_\nu = \tilde{T}_{\nu_1} \cdots \tilde{T}_{\nu_{|\nu|}}$ for all $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$, then there exists a unital $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\pi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_X$ to $\mathcal{X}$ such that $\tilde{\pi}(S_a) = \tilde{T}_a$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, and its restriction to $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{O}_X)$ coincides with π .

Statement 3.4.2 (Lemma 3.1 of [14]). *The correspondence Φ defined by*

$$\Phi(S_\mu A_\nu S_\mu^*) = 1_{C(\mu) \cap \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(C(\nu)))}, \quad \mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(X)$$

gives rise to an isomorphism from the abelian C^ -subalgebra of $\mathcal{O}_X$ generated by $S_\mu A_\nu S_\mu^*$, $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(X)$ onto $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{X^+}$.*

Unfortunately Statement 3.4.2 and thus many of the results in [13], [14], [17] and [18] are not true (cf. [3]). But it is easy to see that Theorem 3.4.1, Statement 3.4.2 and thus all of the results in [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [17] and [18] are true if we replace $\mathcal{O}_X$ by $\mathcal{O}_{X^+}$ (of course provided that there are not any other mistakes).

Many of these results and their proof easily generalized to $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ for every one-sided shift space Λ . If we for example make the following definition:

Definition 3.4.3. *A one-sided shift space Λ is said to be irreducible in past equivalence if for any $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $y \in \Lambda$ and a sequence $(x^k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ of Λ with $x^k \sim_k x^{k+1}$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a number N and a word $\mu \in \mathcal{B}_N(\Lambda)$ such that $y \sim_l \mu x^{l+N}$; and it is said to be aperiodic in past equivalence if for any $l \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a number N such that for any pair $x, y \in \Lambda$ there exists a word $\mu \in \mathcal{B}_N(\Lambda)$ such that $y \sim_l \mu x$.*

Then we have:

Theorem 3.4.4 (Theorem 1.4 of [13]). *If a one-sided shift space Λ is irreducible in past equivalence and has an aperiodic point, then the C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is simple. In particular, if a one-sided shift space Λ is aperiodic in past equivalence and has more than one point, then the C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is simple and purely infinite.*

As a matter of facts one can prove the following Theorems:

Theorem 3.4.5. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Between each pair of the following lattices there exists an ordering preserving, bijective map.*

- a) *The lattice of ideals $\mathcal{I}$ in $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ such that $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(\mathcal{I}) \subseteq \mathcal{I}$.*
- b) *The lattice of ideals $\mathcal{J}$ in $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ such that $S_\mu X S_\nu^*, S_\mu^* X S_\mu \in \mathcal{J}$ for every $X \in \mathcal{J}$ and every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$ with $|\mu| = |\nu|$.*
- c) *The lattice of ideals $\mathcal{M}$ in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ such that $\tilde{\phi}_\Lambda(\mathcal{M}) \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_a(\mathcal{M}) \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$.*
- d) *The lattice of subsets G of Λ such that*

$$\forall x \in G \exists l \in \mathbb{N} : \Lambda^l(x) \subseteq G,$$

and

$$\sigma(G), \sigma^{-1}(G) \subseteq G.$$

Theorem 3.4.6. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. If every subset $G_0 \neq \Lambda$ of Λ such that*

$$\forall x \in G_0 \exists l \in \mathbb{N} : \Lambda^l(x) \subseteq G_0,$$

and

$$\sigma(G_0), \sigma^{-1}(G_0) \subseteq G_0,$$

is open, and the one-sided shift space $\Lambda \setminus G_0$ satisfies condition (I); then for every ideal $\mathcal{I}$ in $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is $\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Lambda}(\mathcal{I}) \subseteq \mathcal{I}$, and $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda/\mathcal{I} \cong \mathcal{O}_{\Lambda \setminus G}$, where G is the subset of Λ that correspond to $\mathcal{I}$ under the bijection of Theorem 3.4.5.

Matsumoto has in [12] proved that $\mathcal{O}_X \rtimes \mathbb{T}$ is stably isomorphic to an AF-algebra and hence that $\mathcal{O}_X$ is nuclear and satisfies the Universal Coefficient Theorem in the sense of Rosenberg and Schochet (cf. [24]) for every two-sided shift space X ; and he has used this to compute the K-theory of $\mathcal{O}_X$. Unfortunately the proof of this does not generalize to $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ for every one-sided shift space Λ (but it of course works for those one-sided shift spaces Λ , where $\Lambda = X^+$ for a two-sided shift space X). So we have to use another method to compute the K-theory of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$, and we will do that in section 4.4.

Notes

Theorem 3.1.1 is inspired by Theorem 4.9 of [11], but the proofs are distinct.

The last part of Section 3.3 is a generalization of Section 5 of [11] and the ideas presented here essentially goes back to [6]. The definition of l -past equivalent, the definition of condition (I) and Proposition 3.3.6 are taken from [13]. Theorem 3.3.15 is a generalization of Theorem 2.13 of [6] and Theorem 4.9 of [11].

Theorem 3.4.5 is an adapted version of Theorem 6.8 of [13], and Theorem 3.4.6 is inspired by Theorem 2.5 of [5] and Theorem 4.3 of [8].

Chapter 4

Conjugacy invariants

In this chapter we will see that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ gives rise to some invariants for one-sided shift spaces. We first show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ itself and $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ are invariants, and then we compute $K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))$ and the KK^{nuc} - and K -theory of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$. Finally we discuss the relation between these invariants and some of the invariants Matsumoto has defined in [16].

4.1 $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is an invariant

We will now show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is an invariant for one-sided shift spaces. We will do that by showing that if two one-sided shift spaces Λ and Γ are conjugate, then $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$ are isomorphic as Hilbert bimodules, and it then follows that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{O}_\Gamma$ are isomorphic.

Definition 4.1.1. *Let $\mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{X}'$ be C^* -algebras, $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$ and $(\mathcal{H}', \phi')$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}'$. If there exist a $*$ -isomorphism $\psi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}'$ and a bijective map $T : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}'$ such that*

$$\langle T\xi, \zeta \rangle = \psi(\langle \xi, T^{-1}\zeta \rangle),$$

and

$$T(\phi(X)\xi) = \phi'(\psi(X))(T\xi)$$

for all $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$, $\zeta \in \mathcal{H}'$, $X \in \mathcal{X}$; then we say that (T, ψ) is an Hilbert bimodule isomorphism, $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ and $(\mathcal{H}', \phi')$ are isomorphic and we write $\mathcal{H} \cong \mathcal{H}'$.

Theorem 4.1.2. *Let $\mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{X}'$ be C^* -algebras, $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}$ and $(\mathcal{H}', \phi')$ a Hilbert bimodule over $\mathcal{X}'$. If (T, ψ) is a Hilbert bimodule isomorphism from $\mathcal{H}$ to $\mathcal{H}'$, then there exists a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_\mathcal{H}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$, sending $\iota(X)$ to $\iota(\psi(X))$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and S_ξ to $S_{T\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$.*

Proof. For each $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ set $\tilde{T}_\xi = S_{T\xi} \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$ and set $\Psi = \iota \circ \psi$. Then Ψ is a *-homomorphism from $\mathcal{X}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$.

Since $\alpha T\xi + \beta T\zeta = T(\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta)$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$, it follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\tilde{T}_\xi + \beta\tilde{T}_\zeta &= \alpha S_{T\xi} + \beta S_{T\zeta} \\ &= S_{\alpha T\xi + \beta T\zeta} \\ &= S_{T(\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta)} \\ &= \tilde{T}_{\alpha\xi + \beta\zeta} \end{aligned}$$

for every $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$.

Since $(T\xi)\psi(X) = T(\xi X)$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, it follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_\xi \Psi(X) &= S_{T\xi} \iota(\psi(X)) \\ &= S_{(T\xi)\psi(X)} \\ &= S_{T(\xi X)} \\ &= \tilde{T}_{\xi X} \end{aligned}$$

for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $X \in \mathcal{X}$.

Since $\phi'(\psi(X))(T\xi) = T(\phi(X)\xi)$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, it follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(X)\tilde{T}_\xi &= \iota(\psi(X))S_{T\xi} \\ &= S_{\phi'(\psi(X))(T\xi)} \\ &= S_{T(\phi(X)\xi)} \\ &= \tilde{T}_{\phi(X)\xi} \end{aligned}$$

for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$ and every $X \in \mathcal{X}$.

Since $(T\xi) \otimes (T\zeta)^* = T \circ (\xi \otimes \zeta^*) \circ T^{-1}$ for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$ and $T \circ \phi(X) \circ T^{-1} = \phi'(\psi(X))$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$, it follows from Proposition 2.1.2 that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{(1)}(\xi \otimes \zeta^*) &= \tilde{T}_\xi \tilde{T}_\zeta^* \\ &= S_{T\xi} S_{T\zeta}^* \\ &= \iota^{(1)}((T\xi) \otimes (T\zeta)^*) \\ &= \iota^{(1)}(T \circ (\xi \otimes \zeta^*) \circ T^{-1}) \end{aligned}$$

for every $\xi, \zeta \in \mathcal{H}$ and hence

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{(1)}(\phi(X)) &= \iota^{(1)}(T \circ \phi(X) \circ T^{-1}) \\ &= \iota^{(1)}(\phi'(\psi(X))) \\ &= \iota(\psi(X)) \\ &= \Psi(X) \end{aligned}$$

for every $X \in \mathcal{I}$.

Thus it follows from Theorem 2.1.6 that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\Psi}$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$ that sends $\iota(X)$ to $\Psi(X) = \iota(\psi(X))$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and S_{ξ} to $\tilde{T}_{\xi} = S_{T\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$. In the same way we get that there exists a $*$ -homomorphism $\tilde{\Psi}'$ from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ that sends $\iota(X)$ to $\iota(\psi^{-1}(X))$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}'$ and S_{ξ} to $S_{T^{-1}\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'$. Since $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ is generated by $\iota(\mathcal{X})$ and S_{ξ} , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$, and $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$ is generated by $\iota(\mathcal{X}')$, and S_{ξ} , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'$, it follows that $\tilde{\Psi}$ and $\tilde{\Psi}'$ are each others inverse, and hence that $\tilde{\Psi}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism from $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$ to $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}'}$ sending $\iota(X)$ to $\iota(\psi(X))$ for every $X \in \mathcal{X}$ and S_{ξ} to $S_{T\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}$. $\square$

Theorem 4.1.3. *If two one-sided shift spaces Λ and Γ are conjugate, then $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda} \cong \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma}$ and $\mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda} \cong \mathcal{H}'_{\Gamma}$.*

Proof. Let $\psi : \Lambda \rightarrow \Gamma$ be a conjugacy. Then we can define a $*$ -isomorphism $\Psi : \mathfrak{B}(\Gamma) \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}(\Lambda)$ by setting $\Psi(f)(x) = f(\psi(x))$ for every $f \in \mathfrak{B}(\Gamma)$ and every $x \in \Lambda$.

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Gamma)$. Since $C_{\Gamma}(\mu)$ is clopen and ψ is continuous, $\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu))$ is clopen and hence compact. So since $C_{\Lambda}(\nu)$, $\nu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ is a basis for the topology of Λ , there exist a finite number of words $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_r \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ such that

$$\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu)) = \bigcup_{k=1}^r C_{\Lambda}(\mu_k).$$

Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}(\Gamma)$ and let $\mu_1, \dots, \mu_r, \nu_1, \dots, \nu_s \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$ such that $\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu)) = \bigcup_{k=1}^r C_{\Lambda}(\mu_k)$ and $\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\nu)) = \bigcup_{k=1}^s C_{\Lambda}(\nu_k)$. Since both ψ and ψ^{-1} commute with the shift, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu) \cap \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(C_{\Gamma}(\nu)))) &= \psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu)) \cap \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\nu)))) \\ &= \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^r C_{\Lambda}(\mu_k) \right) \cap \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^s \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(C_{\Lambda}(\nu_k))) \right), \end{aligned}$$

so it follows from Lemma 3.3.4 that

$$\Psi \left(1_{C_{\Gamma}(\mu) \cap \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(C_{\Gamma}(\nu)))} \right) = 1_{\psi^{-1}(C_{\Gamma}(\mu) \cap \sigma^{-|\mu|}(\sigma^{|\nu|}(C_{\Gamma}(\nu)))} \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}.$$

Hence $\Psi(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma}) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}$. In the same way we can prove that $\Psi^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}) \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma}$, so $\Psi(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma}) = \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}$, and thus $\Psi|_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma}} : \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Gamma} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\Lambda}$ is a $*$ -isomorphism.

Define $T : \mathcal{H}'_{\Gamma} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}'_{\Lambda}$ by

$$T(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_{\Gamma}} = \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_{\Gamma}} \tilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_{\Gamma}(a)})) \Psi(f_a) \right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_{\Lambda}}$$

and $S : \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$ by

$$S(g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} = \left(\sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \tilde{\lambda}_a (\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)})) \Psi^{-1}(g_b) \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}.$$

Let $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$, $b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$ and $x \in \Gamma$. If $ax \in \Gamma$ and $(\psi^{-1}(ax))_1 = b$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{-1}(ax) &= (\psi^{-1}(ax))_1 \sigma(\psi^{-1}(ax)) \\ &= b\psi^{-1}(\sigma(ax)) \\ &= b\psi^{-1}(x) \end{aligned}$$

and thus $b\psi^{-1}(x) \in \Lambda$ and $(\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)))_1 = a$.

If $b\psi^{-1}(x) \in \Lambda$ and $(\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)))_1 = a$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)) &= (\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)))_1 \sigma(\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x))) \\ &= a\psi(\sigma(b\psi^{-1}(x))) \\ &= a\psi(\psi^{-1}(x)) \\ &= ax \end{aligned}$$

and thus $ax \in \Gamma$ and $(\psi^{-1}(ax))_1 = b$.

Hence $(ax \in \Gamma \wedge (\psi^{-1}(ax))_1 = b) \Leftrightarrow (b\psi^{-1}(x) \in \Lambda \wedge (\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)))_1 = a)$.

So

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{-1} \left(\tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \right) (x) &= \begin{cases} \Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)})(b\psi^{-1}(x)) & \text{if } b\psi^{-1}(x) \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } b\psi^{-1}(x) \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } b\psi^{-1}(x) \in \Lambda \wedge (\psi(b\psi^{-1}(x)))_1 = a \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } ax \in \Gamma \wedge (\psi^{-1}(ax))_1 = b \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)})(ax) & \text{if } ax \in \Gamma \\ 0 & \text{if } ax \notin \Gamma \end{cases} \\ &= \tilde{\lambda}_a (\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)}))(x) \end{aligned}$$

and hence $\Psi^{-1} \left(\tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \right) = \tilde{\lambda}_a (\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)}))$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$ and

$b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle T(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}, (g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \rangle &= \left\langle \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(f_a) \right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda}, (g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \right\rangle \\
&= \sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(f_a^*) g_b \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \Psi(f_a^*) \sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) g_b \\
&= \Psi \left(\left\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}, \left(\sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \tilde{\lambda}_a (\Psi^{-1} (1_{C_\Lambda(b)})) \Psi^{-1}(g_b) \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \right\rangle \right) \\
&= \Psi(\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}, S(g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \rangle)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$ and all $(g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$.

Let $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$, $b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$ and $y \in \Lambda$. If $by \in \Lambda$ and $(\psi(by))_1 = a$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi(by) &= (\psi(by))_1 \sigma(\psi(by)) \\
&= a\psi(\sigma(by)) \\
&= a\psi(y),
\end{aligned}$$

and thus $a\psi(y) \in \Gamma$.

So for every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Gamma$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f))(y) &= \begin{cases} \Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)} (by)) \Psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f))(y) & \text{if } by \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } by \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} 1_{C_\Gamma(a)}(\psi(by)) \tilde{\lambda}_a(f)(\psi(y)) & \text{if } by \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{if } by \notin \Lambda \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} f(a\psi(y)) & \text{if } by \in \Lambda, (\psi(by))_1 = a \text{ and } a\psi(y) \in \Gamma \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} f(\psi(by)) & \text{if } by \in \Lambda \text{ and } (\psi(by))_1 = a \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
&= \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \tilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(f))(y),
\end{aligned}$$

and hence $\tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f)) = \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \tilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(f))$ for all $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Gamma$, $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$ and $b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
T(\phi'(f)(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}) &= T(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \\
&= \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(\tilde{\lambda}_a(f) f_a) \right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\
&= \left(\tilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(f)) \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \tilde{\lambda}_b (\Psi (1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) \Psi(f_a) \right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\
&= \phi'(\Psi(f)) T(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}
\end{aligned}$$

for all $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$ and all $f \in \widetilde{\mathcal{D}}_\Gamma$.

Since $\Psi^{-1}(\widetilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)}))) = \widetilde{\lambda}_a(\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)}))$ for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$ and $b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$, Ψ , Ψ^{-1} and $\widetilde{\lambda}_a$ are *-homomorphisms and

$$1_{C_\Lambda(b)}1_{C_\Lambda(b')} = \begin{cases} 1_{C_\Lambda(b)} & \text{if } b = b' \\ 0 & \text{if } b \neq b' \end{cases}$$

for $b, b' \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$, we have that

$$\widetilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)}))\widetilde{\lambda}_{b'}(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) = \begin{cases} \widetilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)})) & \text{if } b = b' \\ 0 & \text{if } b \neq b' \end{cases}$$

for all $a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma$ and all $b, b' \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda$; and hence

$$\begin{aligned} TS(g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} &= T\left(\sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \widetilde{\lambda}_a(\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Lambda(b)}))\Psi^{-1}(g_b)\right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \\ &= \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \widetilde{\lambda}_{b'}(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)}))\sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \Psi(\widetilde{\lambda}_a(\Psi^{-1}(1_{C_\Gamma(b)})))g_b\right)_{b' \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \widetilde{\lambda}_{b'}(\Psi(1_{C_\Lambda(a)}))\sum_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \widetilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_\Lambda(a)}))g_b\right)_{b' \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= \left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \widetilde{\lambda}_b(\Psi(1_{C_\Gamma(a)}))g_b\right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= \left(\widetilde{\lambda}_b\left(\Psi\left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} 1_{C_\Gamma(a)}\right)\right)g_b\right)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= (\widetilde{\lambda}_b(1)g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= (1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(b))}g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \\ &= (g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \end{aligned}$$

for all $(g_b)_{b \in \mathfrak{A}_\Lambda} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$.

In the same way one can prove that $ST(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} = (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma}$ for all $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}_\Gamma} \in \mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$.

Hence (T, Ψ) is a Hilbert bimodule isomorphism and $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda \cong \mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$. $\square$

Theorem 4.1.4. *If two one-sided shift spaces Λ and Γ are conjugate, then $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda \cong \mathcal{O}_\Gamma$ and $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)$.*

Proof. It follows from Theorem 4.1.3 that there exists a Hilbert bimodule isomorphism (T, ψ) from $\mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{H}'_\Gamma$. So by Theorem 4.1.2 there exists a *-isomorphism $\Psi : \mathcal{O}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_\Gamma$ such that $\Psi(S_\xi) = S_{T\xi}$ for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_z(\Psi(S_\xi)) &= \alpha_z(S_{T\xi}) \\
&= zS_{T\xi} \\
&= \Psi(zS_\xi) \\
&= \Psi(\alpha_z(S_\xi))
\end{aligned}$$

for every $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$ and every $z \in \mathbb{T}$. Since $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is generated by S_ξ , $\xi \in \mathcal{H}'_\Lambda$, it follows that $\alpha_z \circ \Psi = \Psi \circ \alpha_z$ for every $z \in \mathbb{T}$. So if $X \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{\mathcal{O}_\Gamma}(\Psi(X)) &= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \alpha_z(\Psi(X)) dz \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \Psi(\alpha_z(X)) dz \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{T}} \Psi(X) dz \\
&= \Psi(X),
\end{aligned}$$

and thus $\Psi(X) \in \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)$. So $\Psi(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)$, and in the same way we can prove that $\Psi^{-1}(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. Hence $\Psi(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)) = \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)$, and thus $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Gamma)$. $\square$

Theorem 4.1.4 tells us that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ are invariants for one-sided shift spaces. What is perhaps more useful is that invariants of C^* -algebras (for example K -theory) used on $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ give us invariants for one-sided shift spaces. We will in the following sections compute some of these invariants.

4.2 $K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))$

In this section, Λ will be a one-sided shift space. We will present a formula for $(K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ expressed in terms of the l -past equivalence classes of Λ .

Lemma 4.2.1. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$, and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$. Then for $k \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ we have that $A_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) \neq 0$ if and only if $\mu \in \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^l)$.*

Proof. This follows from the fact that $\iota^{-1}(A_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})) = 1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C(\mu)) \cap \mathcal{E}_i^l}$. $\square$

Let F be a finite set. Then we denote by $M_F(\mathbb{C})$ the set of matrices over F with entries in $\mathbb{C}$. For a finite number m of finite sets $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_m$ and $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$, $i, j \in F_n$ we let $e(n, i, j)$ be the (i, j) 'th standard matrix unit in $M_{F_n}(\mathbb{C})$, i.e., the matrix whose (i, j) 'th entry is 1 and whose other entries are 0; and we let

$$e_{(i,j)}^n = (0, 0, \dots, e(n, i, j), 0, \dots, 0) \in \bigoplus_{k=1}^m M_{F_k}(\mathbb{C}).$$

Then the following Proposition follows from Lemma 2.4.5, Proposition 3.3.5 and Lemma 4.2.1:

Proposition 4.2.2. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. Then the map*

$$S_{\mu^l} \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l} \right) S_{\nu}^* \mapsto e_{(\mu, \nu)}^i$$

*extends to a *-isomorphism θ_k^l from $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ to $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{m(l)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^l)}(\mathbb{C})$.*

For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ we let

$$I_l(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 4.2.3. *For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$ and each $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ is*

$$\mathcal{E}_j^l = \bigcup_{I_l(i, j)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}.$$

Proof. From the definition of $I_l(i, j)$ it follows that

$$\bigcup_{I_l(i, j)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l.$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{E}_j^l$. Then there exists a $h \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ such that $x \in \mathcal{E}_h^{l+1}$. It is easy to check that $\mathcal{E}_h^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$, so $x \in \mathcal{E}_h^{l+1} \subseteq \bigcup_{I_l(i, j)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}$. Hence

$$\mathcal{E}_j^l = \bigcup_{I_l(i, j)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}.$$

□

Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. It is easy to check that if $\mu \in \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)$ and $I_l(i, j) = 1$, then $\mu \in \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})$. So there exists a *-homomorphism $\hat{I}_k^l$ from $\bigoplus_{j=1}^{m(l)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)}(\mathbb{C})$ to $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})}(\mathbb{C})$ given by

$$e_{(\mu, \nu)}^j \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) e_{(\mu, \nu)}^i.$$

Denote by ι_k^l the inclusion of $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ into $\mathcal{F}_k^{l+1}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. Then we have:

Lemma 4.2.4. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. Then the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{\iota_k^l} & \mathcal{F}_k^{l+1}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \\ \theta_k^l \downarrow & & \downarrow \theta_k^{l+1} \\ \bigoplus_{j=1}^{m(l)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)}(\mathbb{C}) & \xrightarrow{\hat{I}_k^l} & \bigoplus_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})}(\mathbb{C}). \end{array}$$

Proof. It follows from Lemma 4.2.3 that

$$1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} = \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}}$$

for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_k^{l+1} \left(\iota_k^l \left(S_{\mu\iota} \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} \right) S_{\nu}^* \right) \right) &= \theta_k^{l+1} \left(S_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) \iota \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}} \right) S_{\nu}^* \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) e_{(\mu, \nu)}^i \\ &= \hat{I}_k^l e_{(\mu, \nu)}^j \\ &= \hat{I}_k^l \left(\theta_k^l \left(S_{\mu\iota} \left(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} \right) S_{\nu}^* \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and every $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{B}_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)$. Hence the diagram commutes. $\square$

Let F be a finite set and $i_0 \in F$. Then we denote by e_{i_0} the element in $\mathbb{Z}^F$ for which

$$e_{i_0}(i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = i_0 \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

For $1 \leq k \leq l$ let $M_k^l = \{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\} \mid \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_i^l) \neq \emptyset\}$. Since $i \in M_k^{l+1}$ if $j \in M_k^l$ and $I_l(i, j) = 1$, there exists a positive, linear map from $\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}$ to $\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^{l+1}}$ given by

$$e_j \mapsto \sum_{i \in M_k^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) e_i.$$

We denote this map by I_k^l . Then we have:

Proposition 4.2.5. *For every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is*

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))) \cong \varinjlim ((\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}, (\mathbb{Z}^+)^{M_k^l}), I_k^l).$$

More precisely: the map $[S_{\mu\iota}(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l})S_{\nu}^]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}$ extends to an isomorphism from $(K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ to $\varinjlim ((\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}, (\mathbb{Z}^+)^{M_k^l}), I_k^l)$.*

Proof. Since

$$\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) = \overline{\bigcup_{l=k}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)},$$

we have that

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))) \cong \varinjlim((K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))), K_0(l_k^l)),$$

and then it follows from Lemma 4.2.4 that the map

$$[S_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) S_\nu^*]_0 \rightarrow e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}$$

extends to an isomorphism from $(K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ to $\varinjlim((\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}, (\mathbb{Z}^+)^{M_k^l}), I_k^l)$. $\square$

For a subset $\mathcal{E}$ of Λ and a $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^\mathbb{N})$ we let $\mu\mathcal{E} = \{\mu x \in \Lambda \mid x \in \mathcal{E}\}$. For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ we let

$$A_l(i, j, a) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 4.2.6. *For each $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ is*

$$\{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\} = \bigcup_{A_l(i, j, a)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}.$$

Proof. From the definition of $A_l(i, j, a)$ it follows that

$$\bigcup_{A_l(i, j, a)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\}.$$

Let $x \in \{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\}$ and let $h \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ such that $x \in \mathcal{E}_h^{l+1}$. It is easy to check that $ay \in \mathcal{E}_j^l$ for every $y \in \mathcal{E}_h^{l+1}$. Hence $\mathcal{E}_h^{l+1} \subseteq \{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\}$, and thus $x \in \mathcal{E}_h^{l+1} \subseteq \bigcup_{A_l(i, j, a)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}$. Hence

$$\{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\} = \bigcup_{A_l(i, j, a)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}.$$

$\square$

Let $1 \leq k \leq l$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l+1)\}$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. It is easy to check that if $\mu \in \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)$ and $A_l(i, j, a) = 1$, then $\mu a \in \Lambda_{k+1}(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})$. So there exists a *-homomorphism $\hat{A}_k^l$ from $\bigoplus_{j=1}^{m(l)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)}(\mathbb{C})$ to $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} M_{\Lambda_{k+1}(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})}(\mathbb{C})$ given by

$$e_{(\mu, \nu)}^j \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) e_{(\mu a, \nu a)}^i.$$

Denote by κ_k^l the inclusion of $\mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ into $\mathcal{F}_{k+1}^{l+1}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. Then we have:

Lemma 4.2.7. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. Then the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{F}_k^l(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{\kappa_k^l} & \mathcal{F}_{k+1}^{l+1}(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \\ \theta_k^l \downarrow & & \downarrow \theta_{k+1}^{l+1} \\ \bigoplus_{j=1}^{m(l)} M_{\Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)}(\mathbb{C}) & \xrightarrow{\hat{A}_k^l} & \bigoplus_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} M_{\Lambda_{k+1}(\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1})}(\mathbb{C}). \end{array}$$

Proof. It follows from Lemma 3.3.2 and Lemma 4.2.6 that

$$\begin{aligned} S_a^* \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l}) S_a &= \lambda_a(\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l})) \\ &= \iota(\tilde{\lambda}_a(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l})) \\ &= \iota\left(1_{\{x \in \Lambda \mid ax \in \mathcal{E}_j^l\}}\right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} A_l(i, j, a) \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{k+1}^{l+1}(\kappa_k^l(S_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l}) S_\nu^*)) &= \theta_{k+1}^{l+1}\left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{\mu a} S_a^* \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l}) S_a S_{\nu a}^*\right) \\ &= \theta_{k+1}^{l+1}\left(\sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} S_{\mu a} \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} A_l(i, j, a) \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}}) S_{\nu a}^*\right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) e_{(\mu a, \nu a)}^i \\ &= \hat{A}_k^l e_{(\mu, \nu)}^j \\ &= \hat{A}_k^l(\theta_k^l(S_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l}) S_\nu^*)) \end{aligned}$$

for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$ and every $\mu, \nu \in \Lambda_k(\mathcal{E}_j^l)$. Hence the diagram commutes. $\square$

Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. If $j \in M_k^l$ and there exists an $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ such that $A_l(i, j, a) = 1$, then $i \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}$. Hence there exists a positive, linear map from $\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}$ to $\mathbb{Z}^{M_{k+1}^{l+1}}$ given by

$$e_j \mapsto \sum_{i \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) e_i.$$

We denote this map by A_k^l .

Then we have:

Lemma 4.2.8. *Let $1 \leq k \leq l$. Then the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l} & \xrightarrow{I_k^l} & \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^{l+1}} \\ A_k^l \downarrow & & \downarrow A_k^{l+1} \\ \mathbb{Z}^{M_{k+1}^{l+1}} & \xrightarrow{I_{k+1}^{l+1}} & \mathbb{Z}^{M_{k+1}^{l+2}}. \end{array}$$

Proof. Let $j \in M_k^l$, $h \in M_{k+1}^{l+2}$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$. If $\emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$, then there exists exactly one $i \in M_k^{l+1}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$ and $\emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}$; and there exists exactly one $i' \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_{i'}^{l+1}$ and $\emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_{i'}^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$; and if $a\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} = \emptyset$ or $a\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \not\subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$ then there does not exist a $i \in M_k^{l+1}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$ and $\emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}$; and there does not exist a $i' \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}$ such that $\mathcal{E}_h^{l+2} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_{i'}^{l+1}$ and $\emptyset \neq a\mathcal{E}_{i'}^{l+1} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j^l$. Hence

$$\sum_{i \in M_k^{l+1}} A_{l+1}(h, i, a) I_l(i, j) = \sum_{i \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}} I_{l+1}(h, i) A_l(i, j, a).$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} A_k^{l+1}(I_k^l(e_j)) &= A_k^{l+1} \left(\sum_{i \in M_k^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) e_i \right) \\ &= \sum_{h \in M_{k+1}^{l+2}} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_{l+1}(h, i, a) \sum_{i \in M_k^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) e_h \\ &= \sum_{h \in M_{k+1}^{l+2}} \sum_{i \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} I_{l+1}(h, i) A_l(i, j, a) e_h \\ &= I_{k+1}^{l+1} \left(\sum_{i \in M_{k+1}^{l+1}} \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) e_i \right) \\ &= I_{k+1}^{l+1}(A_k^l(e_j)) \end{aligned}$$

for every $j \in M_k^l$. Hence the diagram commutes. $\square$

For $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $(\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}, \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}^+)$ the inductive limit $\varinjlim (\mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}, (\mathbb{Z}^+)^{M_k^l}, I_k^l)$.

It follows from Lemma 4.2.8 that the A_k^l 's induce a positive, linear map A_k from $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_{k+1}}$.

Theorem 4.2.9. *For every one-sided shift space Λ is*

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))) \cong \varinjlim ((\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}, \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}^+), A_k).$$

More precisely: The map $[S_{\mu^l}(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})S_{\nu^l}^]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^l}$ extend to an isomorphism from $(K_0(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ to $\varinjlim ((\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}, \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}^+), A_k)$.*

Proof. Since

$$\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) = \overline{\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)},$$

we have that

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))) \cong \varinjlim ((K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0(\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))), K_0(\kappa_k)),$$

where κ_k denotes the inclusion of $\mathcal{F}_k^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ into $\mathcal{F}_{k+1}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. So it follows from Proposition 4.2.5, Lemma 4.2.7 and Lemma 4.2.8 that the map $[S_\mu \iota(1_{\mathcal{E}^i}) S_\nu^*]_0 \rightarrow e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_k^i}$ extends to an isomorphism from $(K_0(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ to $\varinjlim ((\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}, \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_k}^+, A_k)$. $\square$

4.3 KK^{nuc} of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$

We will now compute the KK^{nuc} -theory (cf. [26]) of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$. For that we will need the following Theorem proved in [22]:

Theorem 4.3.1. *Let $(\mathcal{H}, \phi)$ be a countably generated Hilbert bimodule over the separable C^* -algebra $\mathcal{X}$, with the property that $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{H})$ is isometric and let $\mathcal{J} = \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{H})) \cap \{\langle x, y \rangle \mid x, y \in \mathcal{H}\}$.*

If $\mathcal{Y}$ is any separable C^ -algebra, then the following six term sequences are exact:*

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{J}) & \xrightarrow{\otimes(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}])} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{X}) & \xrightarrow{\iota_*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}) \\ \uparrow \delta & & & & \downarrow \delta \\ KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}) & \xleftarrow{\iota_*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{X}) & \xleftarrow{\otimes(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}])} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{J}) \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xleftarrow{(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}]) \otimes} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xleftarrow{\iota_*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{Y}) \\ \downarrow \delta & & & & \uparrow \delta \\ KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xrightarrow{\iota_*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xrightarrow{(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}]) \otimes} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{Y}) \end{array}$$

where ι_* (respectively ι^*) are the maps induced on KK^{nuc} by the inclusion $\iota : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{H}}$, $\otimes(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}])$ (respectively $(\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}]) \otimes$) are the maps obtained by

right (respectively left) Kasparov multiplication with the element $\iota_{\mathcal{J}} - [\mathcal{H}] \in KK(\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{X})$, where $\iota_{\mathcal{J}}$ is the inclusion of $\mathcal{J}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ and $[\mathcal{H}]$ is the class in $KK(\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{X})$ defined by the Kasparov module $(\mathcal{H}, \phi, 0)$, and δ are the boundary maps corresponding to the Toeplitz extension for $\mathcal{H}$.

Theorem 4.3.2. *For every one-sided shift space Λ and every separable C^* -algebra $\mathcal{Y}$ the following six term sequences are exact:*

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}) & \xrightarrow{(i)^* - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\lambda}_a)^*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}) & \xrightarrow{\iota_*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{O}_{\Lambda}) \\
\uparrow \delta & & & & \downarrow \delta \\
KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{O}_{\Lambda}) & \xleftarrow{\iota_*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}) & \xleftarrow{(i)^* - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\lambda}_a)^*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{Y}, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}) \\
\\
KK_0^{nuc}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xleftarrow{(i)^* - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\lambda}_a)^*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xleftarrow{\iota^*} & KK_0^{nuc}(\mathcal{O}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y}) \\
\downarrow \delta & & & & \uparrow \delta \\
KK_1^{nuc}(\mathcal{O}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xrightarrow{\iota^*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y}) & \xrightarrow{(i)^* - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\lambda}_a)^*} & KK_1^{nuc}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}, \mathcal{Y})
\end{array}$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}$ is the ideal in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}$ generated by $1_{\mathcal{E}_0}$, where $\mathcal{E}_0 = \{x \in \Lambda \mid \exists a \in \mathfrak{A} : ax \in \Lambda\}$, ι_* (respectively ι^*) are the maps induced on KK^{nuc} by the inclusion $\iota : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\Lambda}$, $(i)_*$ (respectively $(i)^*$) are the maps induced on KK^{nuc} by the inclusion of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}$ into $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}$, $(\tilde{\lambda}_a)_*$ (respectively $(\tilde{\lambda}_a)^*$) are the maps induced on KK^{nuc} by $\tilde{\lambda}_a$, and δ are the boundary maps corresponding to the Toeplitz extension for $\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}$.

Proof. Since $\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}$ is a countably generated Hilbert bimodule over the separable C^* -algebra $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}$, and $\phi : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda} \rightarrow L(\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda})$ is isometric, we can apply Theorem 4.3.1. It is easy to check that $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda} = \phi^{-1}(\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda})) \cap \{\langle x, y \rangle \mid x, y \in \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}\}$. By definition is $(\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}, \phi, 0) = \oplus_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)$. Let for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}'_a$ be the ideal in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}$ generated by $1 - 1_{\sigma(C(a))}$. Then $(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)$ is isomorphic to $(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0) \oplus (\tilde{\mathcal{A}}'_a, 0, 0)$ as Kasparov $(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\Lambda}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda})$ -modules, and since $(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}'_a, 0, 0)$ is degenerated, we have that $[(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)] = [(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)]$. So

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}] &= [(\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda}, \phi, 0)] \\
&= [\oplus_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} (\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)] \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} [(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_a, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)] \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} [(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda}, \tilde{\lambda}_a, 0)]
\end{aligned}$$

and hence the two six term sequences are exact. $\square$

4.4 K-theory for $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$

In this section Λ will denote a one-sided shift space. We want to compute the K -theory of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ expressed in terms of the l -past equivalence classes of Λ . We begin by computing $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)$ and $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda)$ and then use Theorem 4.3.2 to compute $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and $K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$.

Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. It is easy to check that

$$\mathcal{E}_0 = \bigcup_{i \in M_1^l} \mathcal{E}_i^l,$$

so

$$1_{\mathcal{E}_0} = \sum_{i \in M_1^l} 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l},$$

and it then follows from Proposition 3.3.5 that $(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})_{i \in M_1^l}$ is a basis for $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda$. Hence we have the following Lemma:

Lemma 4.4.1. *For every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists a $*$ -isomorphism*

$$\theta^l : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{M_1^l},$$

such that $\theta^l(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) = e^i$ for every $i \in M_1^l$, and there exists a $*$ -isomorphism

$$\theta_0^l : \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{m(l)},$$

such that $\theta_0^l(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}) = e^i$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$.

It follows from Lemma 4.4.1 that for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists an isomorphism $\psi^l : K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}$ such that $\psi^l([1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}]_0) = e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}$ for every $i \in M_1^l$, and there exists an isomorphism $\psi_0^l : K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^{m(l)}$ such that $\psi_0^l([1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}]_0) = e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{m(l)}$ for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$.

Denote for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ by B^l the linear map from $\mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}$ to $\mathbb{Z}^{m(l+1)}$ given by

$$e_j \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} \left(I_l(i, j) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) \right) e_i.$$

Then we have.

Lemma 4.4.2. *For every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a)} & K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{l+1}) \\ \psi^l \downarrow & & \downarrow \psi_0^{l+1} \\ \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l} & \xrightarrow{B^l} & \mathbb{Z}^{m(l+1)}. \end{array}$$

Proof. For every $j \in M_1^l$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0^{l+1} \left(\left(K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a) \right) \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \right) &= \psi_0^{l+1} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \tilde{\lambda}_a(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l}) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \\ &= \psi_0^{l+1} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}} \\ - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}} \end{bmatrix} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} \left(I_l(i, j) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} A_l(i, j, a) \right) e_i \\ &= B^l e_j \\ &= B^l \left(\psi^l \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence the diagram commutes. $\square$

Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $i \in M_1^{l+1}$ if $j \in M_1^l$ and $I_l(i, j) = 1$, there exists a *-homomorphism $\hat{I}^l$ from $\mathbb{C}^{M_1^l}$ to $\mathbb{C}^{M_1^{l+1}}$ given by

$$e^j \mapsto \sum_{i \in M_1^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) e^i.$$

For $l \in \mathbb{N}$ let ι^l be the inclusion of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda$ into $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{l+1} \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda$.

Lemma 4.4.3. *For every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda & \xrightarrow{\iota^l} & \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{l+1} \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda \\ \theta^l \downarrow & & \downarrow \theta^{l+1} \\ \mathbb{C}^{M_1^l} & \xrightarrow{\hat{I}^l} & \mathbb{C}^{M_1^{l+1}}. \end{array}$$

Proof. It follows from Lemma 4.2.3 that $\mathcal{E}_j^l = \bigcup_{I_l(i,j)=1} \mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}$ for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{I}^l(\theta^l(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l})) &= \hat{I}^l e^j \\ &= \sum_{i \in M_1^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) e^i \\ &= \theta^{l+1} \left(\sum_{i \in M_1^{l+1}} I_l(i, j) 1_{\mathcal{E}_i^{l+1}} \right) \\ &= \theta^{l+1}(\iota^l(1_{\mathcal{E}_j^l})) \end{aligned}$$

for every $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m(l)\}$. Hence the diagram commutes. $\square$

Proposition 4.4.4. *For every one-sided shift space Λ is*

$$(K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)) \cong \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}.$$

More precisely: The map $[1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}$ extends to an isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}$.

Proof. Since

$$\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda = \overline{\bigcup_{l=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda},$$

we have that

$$K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) \cong \varinjlim (K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda), K_0(\iota^l)),$$

and then it follows from Lemma 4.4.3 that the map $[1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}$ extend to an isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)$ to $\varinjlim (\mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l}, I_1^l) = \mathbb{Z}_{M_{\Lambda_1}}$. $\square$

In a similar way we can for each $l \in \mathbb{N}$ define a $*$ -homomorphism $\hat{I}_0^l : \mathbb{C}^{m(l)} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{m(l+1)}$ given by

$$e^j \mapsto \sum_{j \in m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) e^i,$$

and if we denote the inclusion of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$ into $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{l+1}$ by ι_0^l then we have.

Lemma 4.4.5. *For every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l & \xrightarrow{\iota_0^l} & \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{l+1} \\ \theta_0^l \downarrow & & \downarrow \theta_0^{l+1} \\ \mathbb{C}^{m(l)} & \xrightarrow{\hat{I}_0^l} & \mathbb{C}^{m(l+1)}. \end{array}$$

For every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by I_0^l the linear map from $\mathbb{C}^{m(l)}$ to $\mathbb{C}^{m(l+1)}$ given by

$$e_j \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{m(l+1)} I_l(i, j) e_i,$$

and we denote $\varinjlim(\mathbb{Z}^{m(l)}, I_0^l)$ by $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}$. Then we have:

Proposition 4.4.6. *For every one-sided shift space Λ is*

$$(K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda)) \cong \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}.$$

More precisely: The map $[1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l}]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{m(l+1)}$ extends to an isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}$.

One can easily check that the following diagram commutes for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^l} & \xrightarrow{B^l} & \mathbb{Z}^{m(l+1)} \\ I_1^l \downarrow & & \downarrow I_0^{l+1} \\ \mathbb{Z}^{M_1^{l+1}} & \xrightarrow{B^{l+1}} & \mathbb{Z}^{m(l+2)}. \end{array}$$

Hence the B^l 's induce a linear map B from $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}$. The following Lemma follows from Lemma 4.4.2.

Lemma 4.4.7. *Denote by ψ the isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}$ and by ψ' the isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}$. Then the following diagram commutes:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a)} & K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) \\ \psi \downarrow & & \downarrow \psi' \\ \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1} & \xrightarrow{B} & \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}. \end{array}$$

Theorem 4.4.8. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. Then*

$$K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0} / B\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1},$$

and

$$K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \ker(B).$$

More precisely: The map

$$[\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}_i^l})]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{m(l)}$$

induces an isomorphism from $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0} / B\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}$.

Proof. It follows from Theorem 4.3.2 that

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a)} & K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) & \xrightarrow{K_0(\iota)} & K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \\
\uparrow \delta & & & & \downarrow \delta \\
K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) & \xleftarrow{K_0(\iota)} & K_1(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) & \xleftarrow{K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a)} & K_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda)
\end{array}$$

Since

$$\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda = \overline{\bigcup_{l=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l},$$

and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_l$ is finite dimensional, $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is an AF-algebra, and since $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda$ is an ideal in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$, it is also AF-algebra (cf. Theorem 6.2.6 in [21]). Hence $K_1(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) = K_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda) = 0$. So $K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \ker(K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a))$ and the map $K_0(\iota) : K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda) \rightarrow K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ induces an isomorphism from $K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda)/(K_0(i) - \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} K_0(\tilde{\lambda}_a))(K_0(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\Lambda))$ to $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$. So it follows from Lemma 4.4.7 that

$$K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda) \cong \ker(B),$$

and the map

$$[\iota(1_{\mathcal{E}^l})]_0 \mapsto e_i \in \mathbb{Z}^{m(l)}$$

induces an isomorphism from $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ to $\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_0}/B\mathbb{Z}_{\Lambda_1}$. $\square$

4.5 Invariants for one- and two-sided shift spaces

Matsumoto has in his outstanding paper [16] defined a number of invariants for two-sided subshifts. Among those are the dimension group, which is an ordered abelian group (Δ_X, Δ_X^+) , and the K -groups, which is a pair $K_0(X), K_1(X)$ of abelian groups. One can easily show that for every two-sided shift space X are

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_{X^+})), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_{X^+}))) \cong (\Delta_X, \Delta_X^+),$$

$$K_0(\mathcal{O}_{X^+}) \cong K_0(X),$$

$$K_1(\mathcal{O}_{X^+}) \cong K_1(X).$$

This is no surprise since Matsumoto based his definition of (Δ_X, Δ_X^+) and $(K_0(X), K_1(X))$ on the K -theory of the C^* -algebra $\mathcal{O}_X$ he has associated to a two-sided shift space X .

Since Theorem 4.1.4 tells us that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and hence $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda), K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and $(K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)))$ are invariants for one-sided shift spaces, it is naturally to generalize the definition of the dimension group and the K -groups to one-sided shift spaces by setting

$$(\Delta_\Lambda, \Delta_\Lambda^+) = (K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))),$$

$$K_0(\Lambda) = K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda),$$

$$K_1(\Lambda) = K_1(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda).$$

But we can do a little better. If we denote by $[I]_0$ the class of the unit of $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ in $K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)$ and $K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda))$, then

$$(K_0(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), K_0^+(\mathcal{F}^\infty(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda)), [I]_0)$$

and

$$(K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda), [I]_0)$$

are invariants for one-sided shift spaces.

One can easily show that if X and Y are two-sided shift spaces such that X^+ and Y^+ are conjugate as one-sided shift spaces, then X and Y are conjugate as two-sided shift spaces. We will now present an example of two two-sided shift spaces X and Y such that X and Y are conjugate as two-sided shift spaces, but X^+ and Y^+ are not conjugate as one-sided shift spaces. This example also shows that although $(K_0(\mathcal{O}_\Lambda), [I]_0)$ is an invariant for one-sided shift spaces, and $K_0(\mathcal{O}_{X^+})$ is an invariant for two-sided shift spaces, $(K_0(\mathcal{O}_{X^+}), [I]_0)$ is not an invariant for two-sided shift spaces.

Example 4.5.1. *Let*

$$X = \{a, b, c\}^{\mathbb{Z}}$$

and

$$Y = \{(y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} \in \{1, 2, \dots, 6\}^{\mathbb{Z}} \mid \forall n \in \mathbb{Z} : A(y_n, y_{n+1}) = 1\},$$

where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Define $\Phi : Y \rightarrow X$ by $\Phi((y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}) = (x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, where

$$x_n = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } y_n = 1, 6 \\ b & \text{if } y_n = 2, 5 \\ c & \text{if } y_n = 3, 4 \end{cases}$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$; and $\Psi : X \rightarrow Y$ by $\Psi((x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}) = (y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, where

$$x_n = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_{n-1} = a \text{ and } x_n = a \\ 2 & \text{if } x_{n-1} = a \text{ and } x_n = b \\ 3 & \text{if } x_{n-1} = a \text{ and } x_n = c \\ 4 & \text{if } x_{n-1} \in \{b, c\} \text{ and } x_n = b \\ 5 & \text{if } x_{n-1} \in \{b, c\} \text{ and } x_n = c \\ 1 & \text{if } x_{n-1} \in \{b, c\} \text{ and } x_n = a \end{cases}$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Then one can check that Ψ and Φ are sliding block codes and that there are each others inverse. Hence X and Y are conjugate as two-sided shift spaces.

It is easy to check that $\Lambda^l(x) = \mathcal{B}^l(\{a, b, c\}^{\mathbb{N}})$ for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ and every $x \in X^+$. So $m(l) = 1$, $M_1^l = \{1\}$ and $I_0^l = I_1^l$ are the identity on $\mathbb{Z}$ for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Hence $\mathbb{Z}_{X_1^+} = \mathbb{Z}_{X_0^+} = \mathbb{Z}$.

$A_l(1, 1, a) = A_l(1, 1, b) = A_l(1, 1, c) = 1$ for every $l \in \mathbb{N}$, so the maps $B^l : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ and are given by $B(n) = -2n$ for every $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, and thus the map $B : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ is also given by $B(n) = -2n$. So it follows from Theorem 4.4.8 that

$$(K_0(\mathcal{O}_{X^+}), [I]_0) \cong (\mathbb{Z}_2, 1).$$

Let $\mathcal{E}_1 = \{y \in Y^+ \mid y_1 \in \{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $\mathcal{E}_2 = \{y \in Y^+ \mid y_1 \in \{4, 5, 6\}\}$. Then

$$\Lambda^l(y) = \begin{cases} \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(Y^+) \mid \mu_{|\mu|} \in \{1, 6\}\} & \text{if } y \in \mathcal{E}_1 \\ \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}^l(Y^+) \mid \mu_{|\mu|} \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}\} & \text{if } y \in \mathcal{E}_2 \end{cases}$$

for all $l \in \mathbb{N}$. So $m(l) = 2$, $M_1^l = \{1, 2\}$ and the maps $I_0^l = I_1^l$ are the identity on $\mathbb{Z}^2$. Hence $\mathbb{Z}_{Y_1^+} = \mathbb{Z}_{Y_0^+} = \mathbb{Z}^2$.

Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\sum_{k=1}^6 A_l(1, 1, k) = \sum_{k=1}^6 A_l(1, 2, k) = 1$ and $\sum_{k=1}^6 A_l(2, 1, k) = \sum_{k=1}^6 A_l(2, 2, k) = 2$. So the map $B^l : \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^2$ is given by the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus the map $B : \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^2$ is also given by the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and it then follows from Theorem 4.4.8 that

$$(K_0(Y^+), [I]_0) \cong (\mathbb{Z}_2, 0).$$

So X^+ and Y^+ can not be conjugate as one-sided shift spaces.

Notes

Theorem 4.1.4 is a generalization of Proposition 2.17 of [6] and of Proposition 5.8 of [11]. Notice that contrary to these two Propositions we do not require that the one-sided shift spaces satisfy condition (I). Notice also that the idea to base the proof on Hilbert bimodules is new.

Section 4.2 is a generalization of Section 3 of [12], and Theorem 4.4.8 is a generalization of Theorem 4.9 of [12], but as mentioned before the proof of Theorem 4.9 of [12] is not based on KK -theory, but on the Pimsner-Voiculescu's six term exact sequence (cf. [23]) and the fact that $\mathcal{O}_X$ and $(\mathcal{O}_X \times_\alpha \mathbb{T}) \times_{\hat{\alpha}} \mathbb{Z}$ are stably isomorphic.

Chapter 5

Sofic shifts

We have in Section 3.2 seen that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is a generalization of the Cuntz-Krieger algebras. We will now show that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is isomorphic to a Cuntz-Krieger algebra, if Λ is a sofic shift.

Let Λ be a one-sided shift space. For every $x \in \Lambda$ we let

$$\Lambda_\infty(x) = \bigcup_{l=1}^{\infty} \Lambda^l(x) = \{\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda) \mid \mu x \in \Lambda\}.$$

We say that two points $x, y \in \Lambda$ are past-equivalent and write $x \sim y$ if $\Lambda_\infty(x) = \Lambda_\infty(y)$.

Let Λ be a one-sided shift space with a finite number of past-equivalence classes and denote this number by m_Λ and denote the past-equivalence classes by $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{m_\Lambda}$. It is easy to check that if $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ and $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ such that $a\mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset$, then there exists a unique $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ such that $a\mathcal{E}_i \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j$.

We let $\mathcal{G}_\Lambda$ be the labeled graph with vertex set $\{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$, and where there for each vertex i and each $a \in \mathfrak{A}$ such that $a\mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset$ is an edge labeled a going from j to i , where j is the unique $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ such that $a\mathcal{E}_i \subseteq \mathcal{E}_j$. This labeled graph is called the left Krieger cover of Λ . Notice that it is left-resolving (i.e. all edges ending at the same vertex have different labels).

Proposition 5.0.2. *Let Λ be a one-sided shift space with a finite number of past-equivalence classes. Then $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda}$.*

Proof. By Proposition 1.0.6 it suffices to show that $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda})$.

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. Then there exists a $x \in \Lambda$ such that $\mu x \in \Lambda$. Let $j_{|\mu|} \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ such that $x \in \mathcal{E}_{j_{|\mu|}}$. Since $\mu_{|\mu|}x \in \Lambda$ there exists a $j_{|\mu|-1} \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ such that $\mu_{|\mu|}x \in \mathcal{E}_{j_{|\mu|-1}}$ and there is an edge from $j_{|\mu|-1}$ to $j_{|\mu|}$ labeled $\mu_{|\mu|}$. Since $\mu_{|\mu|-1}\mu_{|\mu|}x \in \Lambda$ there exists a $j_{|\mu|-2} \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ such that $\mu_{|\mu|-1}\mu_{|\mu|}x \in \mathcal{E}_{j_{|\mu|-2}}$ and there is an edge from $j_{|\mu|-2}$

to $j_{|\mu|-1}$ labeled $\mu_{|\mu|-1}$. By continuing in this way we get a path labeled μ and hence $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda})$. So $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda})$.

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda})$. Then there exists a path α such that $\mathcal{L}(\alpha) = \mu$. Let $x \in \mathcal{E}_{t(\alpha_{|\mu|})}$. Then $\mu x \in \Lambda$. Thus $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. Hence $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda) = \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda})$ and $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\mathcal{G}_\Lambda}$. $\square$

Theorem 5.0.3. *A one-sided shift space is sofic if and only if the number of past-equivalence classes is finite.*

Proof. It follows immediately from Proposition 5.0.2 that a one-sided shift space with a finite number of past-equivalence classes is a sofic shift.

Let $\mathcal{G}$ be a labeled graph. For each $x \in \Lambda_{\mathcal{G}}$ let $V(x)$ be the set of vertices where there initiates an infinite path α such that $\mathcal{L}(\alpha) = x$. Let $x, y \in \Lambda_{\mathcal{G}}$. It is easy to see that if $V(x) = V(y)$ then $x \sim y$. Since the number of vertices is finite this implies that the number of past-equivalence classes is finite. $\square$

For a sofic shift Λ we let B_Λ be the matrix over the edge set $\mathcal{G}_\Lambda$ defined by

$$B_\Lambda(e, f) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t(e) = i(f) \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 5.0.4. *Let Λ be a sofic shift. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda \cong \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$ and $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda \cong \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{m_\Lambda}$ be the past-equivalence classes of Λ . Notice that for each $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{A}^{\mathbb{N}})$ is

$$\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu)) = \bigcup_{\mu \mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset} \mathcal{E}_i. \quad (5.1)$$

From this we get that for each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$

$$\mathcal{E}_i = \left[\bigcap_{\mu \mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset} \sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu)) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{\mu \mathcal{E}_i = \emptyset} \Lambda \setminus \sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu)) \right].$$

By (5.1) we see that there is only a finite number of different sets $\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu))$. So we can for each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$ choose finite sets $M_i \subseteq \Lambda^*$ and $N_i \subseteq \Lambda^*$ such that

$$\mathcal{E}_i = \left[\bigcap_{\mu \in M_i} \sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu)) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{\mu \in N_i} \Lambda \setminus \sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu)) \right].$$

From this we get

$$1_{\mathcal{E}_i} = \left[\prod_{\mu \in M_i} 1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu))} \right] \left[\prod_{\mu \in N_i} (1 - 1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu))}) \right].$$

So $1_{\mathcal{E}_i} \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ for each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda\}$.

Since the $\mathcal{E}_i$'s are mutually disjoint the $1_{\mathcal{E}_i}$'s are mutually orthogonal projections. By (5.1) we have that

$$1_{\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_\Lambda(\mu))} = \sum_{\mu \mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset} 1_{\mathcal{E}_i}.$$

So $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ is generated by $1_{\mathcal{E}_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m_\Lambda$.

Let e, f be edges on the left Krieger cover graph of Λ . It is easy to check that $\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e)) = \sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(f))$ if $t(e) = t(f)$, and $\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e)) \cap \sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(f)) = \emptyset$ if $t(e) \neq t(f)$; and since

$$\sigma^{|\mu|}(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(\mu)) = \begin{cases} \sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(\mu_{|\mu|})) & \text{if } \mu \in \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}) \\ 0 & \text{if } \mu \notin \mathcal{B}(\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}) \end{cases}$$

for every $\mu \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{E}^\mathbb{N})$, there exists a *-isomorphism Ψ from $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$ to $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$ such that $\Psi(1_{\mathcal{E}_{t(e)}}) = 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))}$ for every $e \in \mathcal{E}$.

Define a map $T : \mathcal{H}_\Lambda \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$ by setting

$$T(fa)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} = \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}) \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}},$$

and define a map $S : \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ by setting

$$S(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} = \left(1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T(fa)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \rangle &= \left\langle \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}) \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}}, (g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \right\rangle \\ &= \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)})^* g_e \\ &= \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}^*) g_e \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi(f_a^*) g_e \end{aligned}$$

for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and every $(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}}$, and hence

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, S(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \rangle &= \left\langle (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, \left(1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \right\rangle \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} f_a^* 1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} f_a^* 1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \\
&= \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} f_a^* \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \\
&= \Psi^{-1}(\langle T(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}, (g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \rangle)
\end{aligned}$$

for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ and every $(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \in \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$.

Moreover since $\sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1} \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \right) = 1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))}$ for every $a \in \mathfrak{A}$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
ST(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} &= S \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}) \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \\
&= \left(1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1} \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \right) f_a \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \\
&= (f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}
\end{aligned}$$

for every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$.

It is easy to check that $\Psi(1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(\mathcal{L}(e)))}) \geq 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))}$ and since

$$1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(f))} = \begin{cases} 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} & \text{if } t(e) = t(f) \\ 0 & \text{if } t(e) \neq t(f) \end{cases}$$

for every $e, f \in \mathcal{E}$, and since the left Krieger cover graph is left-resolving, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
TS(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} &= T \left(1_{\sigma(C_\Lambda(a))} \sum_{\mathcal{L}(e)=a} \Psi^{-1}(g_e) \right)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \\
&= \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi(1_{C_\Lambda(\mathcal{L}(e))}) \sum_{\mathcal{L}(f)=\mathcal{L}(e)} g_f \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \\
&= (g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}}
\end{aligned}$$

for every $(g_e)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \in \mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$.

Let $e \in \mathcal{E}$ and $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$. Then for every $x \in \Lambda_{B_\Lambda}$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_{\mathcal{L}(e)}(f) \right) (x) &= \begin{cases} \tilde{\lambda}_{\mathcal{L}(e)}(f)(\mathcal{L}(x)) & \text{if } ex \in \Lambda_{B_\Lambda} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} f(\mathcal{L}(e)\mathcal{L}(x)) & \text{if } ex \in \Lambda_{B_\Lambda} \text{ and } \mathcal{L}(e)\mathcal{L}(x) \in \Lambda \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
&= \begin{cases} f(\mathcal{L}(ex)) & \text{if } ex \in \Lambda_{B_\Lambda} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
&= 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \tilde{\lambda}_e(\Psi(f))(x).
\end{aligned}$$

So $1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_{\mathcal{L}(e)}(f) \right) = 1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \tilde{\lambda}_e(\Psi(f))$ for every $e \in \mathcal{E}$ and every $f \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_\Lambda$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned}
T(\phi(f)(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}) &= T(\tilde{\lambda}_a f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \\
&= \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \Psi \left(\tilde{\lambda}_{\mathcal{L}(e)}(f) \right) \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}) \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \\
&= \left(1_{\sigma(C_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}(e))} \tilde{\lambda}_e(\Psi(f)) \Psi(f_{\mathcal{L}(e)}) \right)_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \\
&= \phi(\Psi(f)) T(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}}
\end{aligned}$$

for every $f \in \mathcal{A}_\Lambda$ and every $(f_a)_{a \in \mathfrak{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_\Lambda$. So (T, Ψ) is a Hilbert bimodule isomorphism from $\mathcal{H}_\Lambda$ to $\mathcal{H}_{\Lambda_{B_\Lambda}}$. $\square$

Corollary 5.0.5. *If Λ is a sofic shift, then $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda \cong \mathcal{O}_{B_\Lambda}$.*

Notes

Corollary 5.0.5 is proved for two-sided shift spaces in [2], but the idea to base the proof on Hilbert bimodules is new. The result for two-sided shift spaces also follows from a result in [20] in case the sofic shift satisfies condition (I). Then left Krieger cover goes back to [9]. The idea to work with the left Krieger cover graphs in connexion with C^* -algebras associated with sofic shifts is Matsumoto's (cf. [19]).

Chapter 6

Postscript

There are many interesting topics and unsolved questions concerning C^* -algebras associated with shift spaces that I would have like to have had time to work on, and I will mention a few of them.

The Cuntz-Krieger algebras provided a lot of new examples of C^* -algebras. We have seen that the C^* -algebras associated with sofic shifts are isomorphic to Cuntz-Krieger algebras, so it is naturally to ask if we get any new C^* -algebras from nonsofic shifts. The answer to this question is yes. Matsumoto has in [15] given an example of a two-sided shift space such that the C^* -algebra associated with it is not isomorphic to any Cuntz-Krieger or Cuntz algebra. But does there exists a one-sided shift space such that the C^* -algebra associated with it is not isomorphic to any C^* -algebra associated with a two-sided shift space?

We know that $\mathcal{O}_{X^+}$ is nuclear for every two-sided shift spaces. Is this true for every one-sided shift space?

We have given a condition for when $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is simple and purely infinite. Can we find a shift space Λ such that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is purely infinite and nonsimple?

We have seen that $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is isomorphic to the C^* -algebra associated with the left Krieger cover of Λ for every sofic shift Λ . A nonsofic shift also have a left Krieger cover, but it is infinite. Exel and Laca have constructed Cuntz-Krieger algebras for infinite matrices (cf. [7]) and hence for infinite graphs so it is naturally to ask if $\mathcal{O}_\Lambda$ is isomorphic to the Cuntz-Krieger algebra for the left Krieger cover graph of Λ for every one-sided shift space Λ .

Bibliography

- [1] A. An Huef and I. Raeburn: *The ideal structure of Cuntz-Krieger algebras*. Ergod. Th. & Dynam. Sys. **17** (1997), 611-624.
- [2] T. M. Carlsen: *On C^* -algebras Associated with Sofic Shifts*, to appear in J. Operator Theory, 2000.
- [3] T. M. Carlsen and K. Matsumoto: *Some remarks on the C^* -algebras associated with subshifts*, in preparation.
- [4] J. Cuntz: *Simple C^* -algebras generated by isometries* Comm. Math. Phys. **57** (1977), 173-185.
- [5] J. Cuntz: *A Class of C^* -algebras and Topological Markov Chains II: Reducible Chains and the Ext-functor for C^* -algebras* Invent. Math. **63** (1981), 25-40.
- [6] J. Cuntz and W. Krieger: *A Class of C^* -algebras of Topological Markov Chains* Invent. Math. **56** (1980), 251-268.
- [7] R. Exel and M. Laca: *Cuntz-Krieger Algebras for Infinite Matrices*, J. Reine Angew. Math. **512** (1999), 119-172.
- [8] T. Kajiwara, C. Pinzari and Y. Watatani: *Ideal Structure and Simplicity of the C^* -algebras Generated by Hilbert Bimodules*, J. Funct. Anal. **159** (1998), 295-322.
- [9] W. Krieger: *On Sofic systems I*. Israel J. Math. **48** (1984), 305-330.
- [10] D. Lind and B. Marcus: *An Introduction to Symbolic Dynamics and Coding*, Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge (1995), New York.
- [11] K. Matsumoto: *On C^* -algebras Associated with Subshifts*. Internat. J. Math. **8** (1997), 357-374.
- [12] K. Matsumoto: *K -theory for C^* -algebras associated with subshifts*, Math. Scand. **82** (1998), 237-255.

- [13] K. Matsumoto: *Dimension groups for subshifts and simplicity of the associated C^* -algebras*, J. Math. Soc. Japan **51** (1999), 679-698.
- [14] K. Matsumoto: *Relations among Generators of C^* -algebras Associated with Subshifts*. Internat. J. Math. **10** (1999), 385-405.
- [15] K. Matsumoto: *On a simple C^* -algebra arising from a certain subshift*, J. Operator Theory **42** (1999), 351-370.
- [16] K. Matsumoto: *Presentations of subshift and their topological conjugacy invariants.*, Documenta Math. **4** (1999), 285-340.
- [17] K. Matsumoto: *On automorphism of C^* -algebras associated with subshifts*, J. Operator Theory **44** (2000), 91-112.
- [18] K. Matsumoto: *Stabilized C^* -algebras constructed from symbolic dynamical systems*. Ergodic Theory Dynam. Systems **20** (2000), 821-841.
- [19] K. Matsumoto: *Bowen-Franks Groups for Subshifts and Ext-groups for C^* -algebras.*, to appear in K-Theory.
- [20] K. Matsumoto: *C^* -algebras associated with presentations of subshifts*, preprint, 2000.
- [21] G. J. Murphy: *C^* -algebras and operator theory*, Academic Press (1990), New York.
- [22] M. V. Pimsner: *A Class of C^* -algebras Generalizing Both Cuntz-Krieger Algebras and Crossed Products by $\mathbb{Z}$ Fields* Inst. Commun., **12**, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, (1997), 189-212.
- [23] M. Pimsner and D. Voiculescu: *Exact sequences for K -groups and Ext-groups of certain cross-product C^* -algebras*, J. Operator Theory, **4** (1980), 93-118.
- [24] J. Rosenberg and C. Schochet: *The Künneth theorem and the universal coefficient theorem for Kasparov's generalized K -functor*, Duke Math. J. **55** (1987), 431-474.
- [25] M. Rørdam, F. Larsen, and N.J. Laustsen: *An introduction to K -theory for C^* -algebras*, LMS Student texts, vol. **49**, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2000.
- [26] G. Skandalis: *Une notion de nuclearité en K -théorie* K-Theory **1** (1988), 549-574.
- [27] S. Smale: *Differentiable Dynamical Systems*. Bull. Amer. Math. Soc. **73** (1967), 747-817.

- [28] B. Weiss: *Subshifts of Finite Type and Sofic Systems*. Monats. Math. **77** (1973), 462-474.